

ISPRA

Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale

Deliverable A5.1 Report on Protocol for design, implementation and maintenance of the NBS for drylands

Project ref. number	LIFE20 PRE/IT/000007
Project title	Remote sensing oriented nature based solutions towards a NEW LIFE FOR DRYLANDS
Project Acronym	NewLife4Drylands

Deliverable title	Report on protocol for design, implementation and maintenance of NBS in drylands
Deliverable number	A5.1
Deliverable version	V1
Contractual date of delivery	31/03/2024
Actual date of delivery	28/03/2024
Online access	-
Diffusion	Public
Nature of deliverable	Technical
Action	A5
Partner responsible	ISPRA
Author(s)	Nicola Alessi, Francesca Assennato, Serena D'Ambrogi, Nicola Riitano, Valentina Rastelli, Anna Luise (ISPRA); Fabrizio Ungaro (CNR-IBE); Christos Georgiadis (HSPN); Cristina Tarantino (CNR-IIA); Marcello Vitale, Vito Emanuele Cambria (SAPIENZA); Vicenç Carabassa, Cristina Domingo, Pau Montero (CREAF); Michalis Probonas, Eri Antaloudaki Popi, Baxevani (UoC)
Editor	Serena D'Ambrogi (ISPRA)

NewLife4Drylands
LIFE20 PRE/IT/000007

This project has received funding from the European Union's LIFE 2020 Programme for the Environment and Climate Action under grant agreement No LIFE20 PRE/IT/000007

Executive summary

This document represents the first deliverable of Action A5, due to be delivered in March 2024. Within the framework of the NewLife4Drylands (NL4DL) project, Action A5 aims to define a list of actions (protocol) for the design, implementation, and maintenance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) in drylands, based on the monitoring model developed in Action A3 and the information gathered from the case studies in Action A4. The establishment of a specific protocol for drylands addressed the lack of tools for practical decision making by administrations in identifying drylands, defining specific actions for restoration, and measuring results. Throughout the project activities (mainly A3, A4, but also A1 and A2), the focus has been placed on the use of Remote Sensing (RS) data, validated by in situ data, to establish a monitoring framework linked to the evaluation of the effectiveness of NBSs at an early stage of the project.

The Protocol adapts and elaborates on the international reference documents (i.e. SER, IUCN, and Canadian protected areas), particularly focusing on activities for the restoration of degraded soils using NBS. In addition, the Protocol explores the integrated use of ground-based data (for short-term monitoring) and RS data (for medium- and long-term monitoring) to identify indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of planned solutions. This approach aims to promote adaptive and collaborative management of the ecological restoration process.

Therefore, the Protocol acts as a support tool for decision makers, including public administrations of Protected Areas (Pas) management, as well as technicians and planners (such as engineers, architects, agronomists and foresters, geologists, surveyors, etc.); it defines a process that addresses both soil degradation restoration and the medium and long-term monitoring of proposed restoration solutions (NBS). Additionally, it serves as a guide for the identification of specific/local solutions (NBS) for the restoration of drylands, starting with the identification of degradation processes. The comprehensive report provides a detailed account (catalogue) of best practices/solutions (NBS) applicable in similar contexts.

Table of Contents

0. ACRONYMS.....	4
1. INTRODUCTION	5
2. NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS FOR THE ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION OF AREAS WITH SOIL DEGRADATION	8
3. THE PROTOCOL FOR DESIGN, IMPLEMENTATION AND MAINTAINANCE OF ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION ACTIVITIES (NBS) IN DRYLANDS: THE PROCESS DESCRIPTION	11
3.1 Identify and describe.....	14
3.1.1 Define the restoration problem(s) that needs to be addressed.....	14
3.1.2 Site Description and related information.....	14
a. General condition inventory	14
b. Legal requirements	15
c. Stakeholder engagement and communication activities	17
3.2 Analyse and planning	20
3.2.1 Decision Support Web tool: description and application of the tool to identify potential Nature-Based Solutions	20
a. Remote Sensing indices in the MM web tool (listed in Annex B table 1).....	21
b. Composite Indices (listed in Annex B table 2).....	22
c. In situ indicators	23
3.2.2 Procedure for medium and long-term monitoring through in situ and RS data.....	27
a. The NL4DL procedure for RS data management and indicator extraction	30
b. The use of RS and ground data: the dual approach procedure	31
3.3 Assess: determining the appropriate restoration objectives and associated activities	33
a. Develop goals and objectives	33
b. Identify reference ecosystem(s) and models	33
c. Ecosystem services assessment	36
d. Cost-Benefit Analysis.....	41
3.4 Planning and design	42
a. Solutions identification.....	42
b. Restoration solutions prescriptions	42
c. Assessment of site tenure security and scheduling of post-treatment maintenance	43
d. Analyze logistics.....	43

e. Establish a process for project review	43
3. 5 Implement and monitor.....	44
a. Protect the site from damage.....	44
b. Engage appropriate participants.....	44
c. Incorporate natural processes.....	44
d. Respond to changes occurring on site	44
e. Ensure compliance	44
f. Communicate with stakeholders	44
a. Design the monitoring process	45
b. Keep records.....	45
c. Evaluate outcomes.....	46
d. Report to interested parties	46
4. RECOMMENDATIONS	47
5. ANNEXES.....	49
4. REFERENCES.....	102

0. ACRONYMS

AGB	Above ground biomass
AGCS	Above ground C stock
AOI	Area of interest
CSA	Case study areas
DURC	Sole Document of Social Security Contribution Regularity
EV	Essential Variable
LC	Land cover
LD	Land degradation
LU	Land use
MM	Decision Support web tool
MLR	Multiple linear regression
NL4DL	NewLife4Drylands project
NBS	Nature based solution
PA	Protected area
RS	Remote Sensing
RSI	Remote Sensing
SDGs	Sustainable development goals
SEC	Soil erosion control
UNEA	United Nations Environment Assembly
VInCA	Appropriate Assessment of Implications for Natura 2000 sites sensu art.6 92/43/CEE Directive
VHR	Very High-Resolution

1. INTRODUCTION

The main objective of the NewLife4Drylands (NL4DL) project is to monitor the application, scalability, and replicability of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) for the restoration of drylands by using satellite-based indicators. This involves establishing a protocol for NBS in drylands, encompassing the identification of drylands characteristics and the design of NBS, and overseeing mid-term and long-term restoration efforts.

This protocol has primarily adopted the approach and the structure of the [International Principles and Standards for the Practice of Ecological Restoration](#) (SER, 2019), hereafter referred to as Standards, adapting them to the specific needs of ecological restoration of drylands. This framework has been customized to cater the specific needs of ecological restoration in drylands.

The Standards serve as an international reference for ecological restoration activities, extending to regions with degraded soils. They situate ecological restoration within a global context, acknowledging its significance in restoring biodiversity and improving human well-being in the face of rapid global transformations. The Standards recognize that effective design, throughout good planning and execution, wide expertise, effort and resources, comprehension of particular social contexts and potential risks, engagement of relevant stakeholders, and adequate monitoring for adaptive management all play crucial roles in achieving improved outcomes. (SER, 2019)

Two additional documents are used as reference for the contents of the Protocol, namely:

- [Principles and Guidelines for ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION in Canada's Protected Natural Areas \(2008\)](#)
- [IUCN, Ecological Restoration for Protected Areas \(2012\).](#)

The Canadian Principles and Guidelines have been developed to guide policymakers and practitioners in the efforts towards the improvement of ecological integrity in Canada's Protected natural areas, including the meaningful engagement of a large group of stakeholders. It sets out Canadian principles and guidelines for ecological restoration and provides a practical framework for making consistent, credible, and informed decisions regarding ecological restoration in protected natural areas.

The IUCN document guides terrestrial, marine, and freshwater PA managers at both system and site levels on the restoration of natural and associated values of PA. Important point: the guide uses the term "restoration for PA" for activities within PA and for activities in connecting or surrounding lands and waters that influence PA values, since restoration immediately outside PA boundaries is sometimes required. In the document, the basic principles of the restoration actions within PAs are:

- *effective ecological restoration that is a restoration that re-establishes and maintains the values of a PA;*
- *efficient ecological restoration that is a restoration that maximizes beneficial outcomes while minimizing costs in time, resources, and effort;*

- *engaging ecological restoration that is a restoration that collaborates with partners and stakeholders, promotes participation, and enhances the visitor experience.*

These documents represent international references for ecological restoration activities in and outside PAs. The consultation of these documents is recommended to investigate and explore specific issues of interest and/or related to specific issues of the site under restoration activities.

The Protocol is developed following the principles and inputs of the cited documents, and integrating the NL4DL project outputs into ecological restoration activity in drylands (through planning, design, implementation, and maintenance):

- a procedure for medium and long-term monitoring of ecosystem restoration interventions (such as NBS) in degraded drylands, using remote sensing (RS) techniques. This allows for long-term monitoring beyond the usual typical short-term, in-field campaigns. It serves to assess the effectiveness of restoration activities and improve sustainable land management;
- an operational tool, the Decision Support web tool (MM), which, starting from the degradation processes, identifies sustainable solutions (NBS) along with indices/indicators related to each degradation processes to monitor the effectiveness of these solutions. The MM is designed for end-users involved in managing and planning PAs. It guides them in evaluating available NBS for restoration activities in soil-degraded areas and provides relevant monitoring elements. This tool aims to reduce the knowledge effort, subjective analysis and helps in prioritizing options.

Together, these tools establish a process for making decisions regarding land and soil restoration, alongside the identification of best practices that can be replicated in similar context.

In the Protocol, the elements described in the reference documents (SER, IUCN and Canadian PAs) are tailored and further elaborated, particularly concerning activities for the restoration of degraded soils using NBS. The Protocol also explores the integrated use of ground-based data (for short-term monitoring) and RS data (for medium and long-term monitoring) to identify indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of planned solutions. This approach is geared, towards fostering adaptive and collaborative management of the ecological restoration process.

Therefore, the Protocol serves three main functions:

- it serves as a support tool for decision-makers, including PA administrators, as well as technicians and planners (such as engineers, architects, agronomists and foresters, geologists, surveyors, etc.), to highlight the main issues for restoration in areas with degraded soils;
- it defines a process that addresses both the process of restoring soil degradation and the medium and long-term monitoring of the effectiveness of proposed restoration solutions (NBS). The process also aims to raise awareness of the needs and opportunities of NBS in drylands;

- it serves as a guide for the identification of specific/local solutions (NBS) for dryland restoration, starting with the identification of degradation processes through a *Catalogue of best practices/solutions (NBS)* applicable in the Mediterranean context.

2. NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS FOR THE ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION OF AREAS WITH SOIL DEGRADATION

Ecosystem restoration and NBS have emerged as crucial approaches for addressing environmental challenges and promoting sustainability (UNEP, 2021). Ecosystem restoration involves assisting the recovery of degraded ecosystems, while NBS leverage the power of nature to effectively tackle environmental problems (IUCN, 2020), including the restoration of degraded ecosystems. Ecosystem restoration includes tailored strategies for specific ecosystems and is commonly used to reverse environmental degradation, usually with NBS. Both approaches aim to enhance biodiversity, improve ecosystem services, and mitigate climate change, providing sustainable benefits to nature and society.

The concept of NBS originated in the late 2000s (MacKinnon et al., 2008; Mittermeier et al., 2008), in the context of finding new solutions to mitigate and to adapt to climate change effects whilst simultaneously protecting biodiversity and improving sustainable livelihoods. The definition of NBS, as adopted by UNEA (UNEA, 2022), has a significant relationship with land degradation: specifically, the definition recognizes that NBS are among the actions that are essential in the global effort to achieve the [Sustainable Development Goals \(SDGs\)](#), including addressing land degradation.

The concept of NBS can thus be defined as an umbrella concept that covers a wide range of ecosystem-related approaches, which can be classified as (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2016):

- (i) ecosystem restoration approaches;
- (ii) specific ecosystem-related approaches, such as ecosystem-based adaptation, mitigation, and disaster risk reduction;
- (iii) infrastructure-related approaches, such as natural infrastructure and green infrastructure;
- (iv) ecosystem-based management approaches, such as integrated coastal zone management and integrated water resources management; and
- (v) ecosystem protection approaches, such as PA management.

Examples of Land Degradation (LD) restoration solutions can include: reforestation and afforestation projects, regenerative agriculture practices, rehabilitation of degraded wetlands, coastal buffers to reduce erosion and flooding, restoring degraded landscapes to enhance their resilience to climate change, vegetated buffer strips to prevent soil erosion, Land Use (LU) planning, regulating development activities, measures to protect and restore coastal ecosystems, creation and management of national parks, wildlife sanctuaries, and nature reserves.

The successful implementation of ecosystem restoration using NBS, relies on the application of strategies that address the specific challenges faced by degraded ecosystems, although it should be noted that in the very recent period, there has been a strong emphasis on the holistic approach to address challenges in the most integrated manner possible. These strategies encompass diverse approaches, from site-specific restoration techniques to landscape-scale conservation efforts. By implementing these strategies, it can be needed to promote the

recovery of ecosystems and harness their inherent resilience to achieve sustainable development. Below are provided examples of specific strategies that can be supportive in the context of different general concepts:

- **Ecological Restoration:** it focuses on returning a degraded ecosystem to its historic ecological structure, functions, and species composition. This strategy involves identifying the root causes of degradation, implementing appropriate interventions, and monitoring the progress of restoration efforts. Ecological restoration can include measures such as reforestation, habitat creation, reintroduction of native species, and the removal of invasive species.
- **Sustainable Land Management:** it integrates ecological, social, and economic factors to ensure the long-term productivity and resilience of ecosystems. This approach involves adopting practices that minimize soil erosion, enhance soil fertility, conserve water resources, and promote sustainable agricultural practices. Techniques such as agroforestry, conservation tillage, and precision agriculture are examples of sustainable land management practices that can contribute to ecosystem restoration (Fleskens, 2019).
- **Green Infrastructure:** it focuses on incorporating natural elements into urban planning and design to enhance ecosystem services and promote environmental quality. This approach includes the strategic placement of green spaces, such as parks, urban forests, and wetlands, to improve air and water quality, reduce urban heat island effects, and provide recreational opportunities. Green infrastructure can contribute to ecosystem restoration by creating interconnected networks of habitats and supporting biodiversity conservation (European Commission, 2020).

BOX 1. Opportunities for European funding of restoration measures

Under the implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy, two new legal frameworks are under discussion for the future of Europe: the Regulation on Nature Restoration Law and the Soil monitoring and resilience Directive.

The European Commission's proposal for a [Regulation on nature restoration \(COM/2022/304 final\)](#) is the first continent-wide, comprehensive law of its kind, which calls for binding targets to restore degraded ecosystems, in particular those with the most potential to capture and store carbon and to prevent and reduce the impact of natural disasters. The regulation is supposed to support benefits from restoring a broad range of EU ecosystems and can be estimated as of the order of EUR 1 860 billion (with costs estimated as of the order of EUR 154 billion). The main costs will stem from the restoration of ecosystems and their maintenance, from foregone incomes and administrative costs to develop common monitoring systems.

The [Proposal for a Soil monitoring and resilience Directive](#), aims to establish a framework to monitor soil health, enhance resilience, reverse degradation and ensure sustainable soil management across Europe. It seeks to provide data on soil health and ensure that EU soils are

in a healthy condition by 2050. The Directive provides a harmonised definition of soil health and fosters measures to regenerate degraded soils, sustainable soil management and remediation of contaminated sites.

The resources to be mobilized for those new frameworks will involve both EU and Member States and still must be defined. A reference was given for the Soil Monitoring Directive together with the Impact assessment referring to main funding tools as:

- [Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe”](#)
- [Horizon Europe](#) (Pillar I ‘Excellent Science’; Pillar II ‘Global challenges and European industrial competitiveness’ and Pillar III ‘Innovative Europe’)
- [The Common Agriculture Policy](#), in particular the [European Agriculture Guarantee Fund](#) (EAGF) and the [European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development](#) (EAFRD).
- [Cohesion Policy Funds](#) (CPF) including [European Regional Development Fund](#) (ERDF) and [Interreg programmes](#) and [Just Transition Fund](#) (JTF)
- [Programme for Environment and Climate Action](#) (LIFE)
- [Technical Support Instrument](#) (TSI)
- [Recovery and Resilience Facility](#) (RRF)
- [InvestEU](#)

3. THE PROTOCOL FOR DESIGN, IMPLEMENTATION AND MAINTAINANCE OF ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION ACTIVITIES (NBS) IN DRYLANDS: THE PROCESS DESCRIPTION

The process provides recommended steps for an ecological restoration activity. The proposed pathway (Figure 1) represents the adaptive process that plays a crucial role in creating an effective, efficient, and engaging ecological restoration effort.

In this view, it is crucial to recognise that restoration is not linear, and that some steps and actions may be undertaken simultaneously, or in a different order, or repeated. This is because adaptive management requires an iterative process of defining goals and objectives, conducting field trials to fill information gaps and test multiple alternative approaches, learning from restoration through effective monitoring and evaluation, and applying lessons learned to planning, implementation and ongoing management. (SER, 2019).

Fig. 1 The process for planning and implementing and maintenance ecological restoration activities in drylands.

The **Identify and describe** step includes the identification and evaluation causes, extent, and intensity of degradation, considering the site and its context. The preliminary collection of data should record the status of current abiotic conditions, and detect the characteristics of degradation drivers and threats, but also set the framework of legal requirements link to the restoration activities and the stakeholder engagement process contents. At this stage of the process, it is extremely important that the information is shared with stakeholders

Having defined this framework of information, the user can enter within restoration activities **Analyse and planning** step using the Decision support Web Tool prepared in the NL4DL project (MM). The outputs of the tool (potential applied restoration solutions NBS) for the degradation process individuated, and indicators useful to monitor it, can guide the user to evaluate, following the procedure and the dual approach proposed by the NL4DL project, the availability and use of the data useful to monitor the ecosystems affected by the restoration interventions.

The next step (**Assess**) focuses on evaluating and determining the appropriate restoration objectives and associated activities, based on the definition of the ecosystem reference, the restoration objectives, the specific goals and objectives, and the assessment of the potential positive and/or negative impacts of the restoration activities. At this stage of the process, it is extremely important that decisions are made and developed based on consultation with stakeholders, rights holders, and experts (defined in the Context inventory), considering the ecological, socio-economic, and cultural contexts as costs and benefits, as well as legal and financial constraints. Design step should also anticipate all on-the-ground activities that will take place during project implementation.

The identification (**Design**) of the more effective NBS for the local situation should be based on:

- the restoration problem assessment and context inventory step repository,
- the different potential effective solutions to mitigate the degradation processes (Catalogue of sustainable restoration solutions (NBS) (ANNEX A) and the relative RS indicators and in situ indicators to monitoring the degradation processes before and after the solution implementation;
- the definition of the ecosystem reference, the restoration objectives, the specific goals and objectives, and the assessment of the potential positive and/or negative impacts of the restoration activities.

This step includes a detailed definition of all the operative information and features.

The next step (**Implement and monitor**) includes all the technical and communication activities necessary to prevent damage during the implementation phase of the remediation work and to respond to any unexpected events during the work, as well as the short and long-term needs of the site once the planned implementation activities have been completed. In addition, the Monitoring step focuses on measuring the progress of the restoration, the achievement of the restoration goals and objectives, allowing adaptive management of the restoration process for corrections and modifications to the actions foreseen in the planning

and design phase, and providing the opportunity to share lessons learned. Also at this step, the involvement and discussion with the local stakeholders is crucial.

The framework of the different steps of the process represents the main results of the A5 activity; the contents of the steps are based on the contents and indications of the analysed international reference documents (SER, 2019; IUCN, 2012; Canada, 2008), implemented from the procedures, approaches and tools elaborated in areas with degraded soils during the NL4DL project activities. The following paragraphs describe the different steps of a general and non-linear pathway, which should be adapted to local conditions and possibilities.

3.1 Identify and describe

This phase is particularly important for projects within PAs, especially those where restoration has not been previously carried out or where previous restoration efforts have not been successful. Above all, in alignment with the referenced documents, the Protocol underscores that adaptive management is a vital component of ecological restoration (IUCN, 2020).

3.1.1 Define the restoration problem(s) that needs to be addressed

The problem statement is a key component of the restoration process: in fact, if defined precisely enough, the problem statement will also help to define the necessary responses and the monitoring requirements needed to assess solutions effectiveness (IUCN, 2012).

Regardless of the information base available, the problem statement considers:

1. *The problem*: a description of the problem regarding ecosystem/habitat/soil degradation (as landscape modification, aridification, forest fires, hydrological modification, overgrazing, soil salinization, soil organic matter decline, soil erosion by water and wind, decline in vegetation community functioning, decline in vegetation cover/biomass, habitat loss).
2. *The causes*: where known, a description of the immediate and any underlying causes of the problem (the drivers of land degradation processes in the NL4DL case studies have been climate change, natural disaster/extreme events, land use change, unsustainable farming or water and forestry practices, poor land use planning, pollution, waste dumping, between other anthropogenic pressures).
3. *Why restoration*: a justification of why restoration is appropriate and likely to be successful. This provides evidence that the restored habitats or species will not succumb to the pressures that caused the original problems.

3.1.2 Site Description and related information

a. General condition inventory

Before detailed planning can proceed, preliminary information about target ecosystems should be collected to assess their condition and define any ongoing degradation phenomena ongoing and/or restoration challenges. The baseline inventory documents the causes, intensity, and extent of degradation, and describes the effects of degradation on the biota and physical environment relative to the ecosystem attributes as absence of threats, physical conditions, species composition, structural diversity, ecosystem function, external exchanges. (SER, 2019)

Accordingly, plans should:

- Identify native, ruderal, and nonnative species persisting on the site, particularly threatened species or communities, and invasive species.
- Record the status of current abiotic conditions (through photographs, bibliography, public databases and other means) including dimensions, configuration, and physical and chemical condition of streams, water bodies, water column, land surfaces, soils, or any other material elements, relative to prior or changing conditions;
- Detect the type and degree of drivers and threats that have caused degradation on the site and ways to eliminate, mitigate, or adapt to them. This information is input for the MM described in 3.2.1. This includes the assessment of:

- a. Historical, current, and anticipated impacts within and external to the site (e.g., over-utilization, sedimentation, fragmentation, pest plants and animals, hydrological impacts, contamination, altered disturbance regimes) and ways to manage, remove, or adapt to them;
- b. Description of needs for genetic diversity supplementation for species reduced to non-viable populations due to fragmentation;
- c. Current and anticipated effects of climate change (e.g., temperature, rainfall, sea level, marine acidity) on species and genotypes concerning likely future viability;
- d. Identify the relative capacity of the biota on site or external to the site to commence and continue recovery with or without assistance.

b. Legal requirements

National, regional, provincial, and municipal legislation, regulations, and policies applicable to the project should be identified and consulted. These requirements may help in the resolution of conflicts between management objectives (i.e., where those objectives are based in law). Extensive legal frameworks guide the management of the PAs in which ecological restoration activities are proposed. A thorough review of any regional and international conservation strategies, goals, programmes, and policies can help define the project. For example, national, regional, or global action plans associated with invasive species or climate change adaptation and mitigation may influence restoration goals (IUCN, 2008). Any relevant case law should also be identified, as should formally plans or policies specific to the region. Similarly, broad strategies at the national level and proposed actions for managing threats such as invasive alien species should be consulted.

It should be noted that, on many occasions as in LIFE project actions, could be possible to have problems in carrying out restoration actions, due to the bureaucratic processes that must be followed in MS, affecting interventions on both public and private lands¹. Sometimes national or regional laws, specific natural sites management plans or competent administration proceedings constitute barriers for the restoration or conservation of those spaces. Administrative and legal issues, in fact, cause very significant delays in the restoration of natural ecosystems, often involving a serious drawback for the timely restoration of damaged PAs (CREAF, 2021).

¹ In Italy the start of restoration activities in PAs is subject to the submission of the VInCA (Appropriate Assessment of Implications for Natura 2000 sites sensu art.6 92/43/CEE Directive) report. In the Alta Murgia Natura 2000 PA, the study site where NL4DL project carried out natural grassland restoration activities according to NBS techniques, it was necessary to submit a VInCA to the Metropolitan City of Bari, which is the responsible territorial organisation in charge of the area's conservation. The document consisted in a request along with a technical report describing all the activities with a timetable and all materials and techniques to be adopted and the analysis of their impacts on the environment. The criteria of not disturbing any habitat and species populations must be followed. Furthermore, a professional technician had to be commissioned for the technical report setting that was requested and a period from one to three months had to wait after the VInCA's delivery before obtaining positive consensus.

BOX 2. The case of Palo Laziale restoration activities (PRIMED Life Project): a long legal story

LIFE PRIMED (LIFE17 NAT/GR/000511) aimed to mitigate the impact of increasing drought and irregular rainfall regimes on Mediterranean coastal habitats by introducing a water distribution system in Palo Laziale, Italy—a protected Natura2000 site. This innovative NBS was engineered to supplement the site's forest ecosystems with additional water sources during dry spells, leveraging a drainage trench to collect rainwater in an underground tank. Solar-powered distribution mechanisms deliver the stored water as needed, ensuring an eco-friendly solution with zero carbon emissions in a delicate natural ecosystem.

Due to overlapping legal conservation regimes - nature, landscape, archaeology, and hydrogeology - applying in this, as in many other areas of the Mediterranean, the project's execution required securing permissions from manifold regulatory bodies. Among the competent authorities that were required to be involved were the:

- I. Regional Directorate for Environmental Policies, Waste Cycle and Forest Resources for the VincA (Appropriate Assessment of Implications for Natura 2000 sites sensu art.6 92/43/CEE Directive) report;
- II. Archaeological Superintendence of Lazio and Southern Etruria, responsible for landscape and archaeological heritage (Article 146 of Italian Legislative Decree 42/2004);
- III. Military Engineering Corps for World War II ordnance clearing procedures;
- IV. Metropolitan City Civil Engineering Department for structural verification of the hydraulic project;
- V. Regional Forestry Command of Carabinieri for grounds of public policy;
- VI. Regional Basin Authority for hydrogeological checks;
- VII. Regional Local Health Authority for health-related concerns;
- VIII. Provincial Labour Inspectorate for tax and social security compliance;
- IX. Municipality of Ladispoli for building permissions;
- X. Site owners for consultation and authorisation on field operations.

The authorisation process, initiated in January 2021, took fifteen months to complete, requiring navigating complex bureaucratic waters, including a multi-actor service conference or silent consent from unrequired participants, and culminated in a detailed report submitted to all relevant authorities, with the final approvals trickling in throughout March 2022. Project coordinators and procedure managers often had to reach out to each authority individually with separate authorisation requests, leading to disparate response times and procedural complexities. The arrangement of necessary field inspections, such as archaeological surveys and military weapon clearances, compulsory to prepare for the hydraulic system's construction, led to additional and unplanned costs and posed potential halts in restoration efforts upon least concern archaeological discoveries, representing an impelling challenge for the financial and task management of the project.

For successful implementation of restoration initiatives in the Mediterranean region, a synchronised dialogue among all levels of competent authorities is essential. National, regional, and local entities must collaborate to create harmonised procedures that effectively balance and prioritise conservation efforts for both natural and cultural values within these ecologically sensitive areas. Without a streamlined process and clear prioritisation guidelines, the likelihood of project delays and fund wastage increases, which can jeopardise the overall success of EU restoration targets. A unified approach that offers guidance and support for practitioners can help align conservation priorities, reduce bureaucratic friction, and enhance the efficiency and impact of ecological restoration projects in the Mediterranean and similar regions. Creating a consensus-driven framework could lead to a more sustainable and culturally respectful approach to environmental stewardship.

c. Stakeholder engagement and communication activities

Stakeholders can help prioritize distribution of restoration actions across the landscape, set project goals (including desired level of recovery), contribute knowledge about ecological conditions and successional patterns to improve development of reference models and engage in participatory monitoring. This engagement should occur at the conceptual phase or well ahead of project initiation, so stakeholders can help define the vision, targets, goals, objectives, but also gaining permission for the proposed work, contributing skills, knowledge, financial, and human resources to the development, implementation, maintenance, and long-term monitoring.

Engagement and training activities should continue throughout the project to provide committed, monitoring, and collaborative knowledge generation and dissemination to help meet social expectations, build capacity and a sense of ownership, maintain support, and input, and identify and assess the ecosystem benefits of the proposed solutions.

Key steps should be:

- Map stakeholder: information about the site as well as an understanding of off-site influences and effects should be used to re-evaluate who should be involved throughout the project duration. Anyone with a legal interest in the project must be engaged at the earliest possible time. Other individuals and organizations with interests or expertise can be brought in at different stages. Finally, substantive, relationship, and process goals and objectives should be considered in developing project budgets (Canadian Parks Council, 2008).
 - Prepare a schedule for stakeholder engagement throughout project lifespan. Where possible, participatory planning and restoration plan co-design are implemented, and local community capacity building and training are included (SER, 2019);
- Perform due diligence to ensure that stakeholder rights, including land tenure, are understood, and respected throughout the restoration process (SER, 2019);
- Develop a communication strategy. (IUCN,2008).

In general, some of the common tools and methods can include surveys, questionnaires, interviews, correspondence, focus/thematic groups, workshops, webinars, forums, seminars, newsletters, blogs, social media, dashboards, feedback mechanisms, newsletters, articles, press releases, pod cast episode, and co-design processes. It can be used as a combination of online and offline tools and methods to reach a wider audience and increase engagement.

Based on the experience of international actions on soil, [A Soil Deal for Europe](#), tested also in the NL4DL project, Living laboratories (or Living labs) and Lighthouses are core elements required to work directly with users in real-life settings. *The users will drastically improve the understanding of the cultural and socio-economic drivers of change, making sure that solutions developed improve soil health, ecosystem services and are in line with people's values, priorities and economic realities* (European Commission, 2021). The Living Labs are defined as “*user-centred, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, which involve land managers, scientists and other relevant partners in systemic research and codesign, testing, monitoring and evaluation of solutions, in real-life settings, to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate adoption.*”, instead the Lighthouses are defined as “*places for demonstration*

of solutions, training and communication that are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement” (European Commission, 2021).

BOX 3. NL4DL Communication activities

Specifically, within NL4DL project framework, partners have followed this communication strategy:

- set the goals of stakeholder engagement and the key messages to be conveyed. Based on these goals, mapping stakeholders in each of the six participating case studies of the project.
- Contact stakeholders to explain the participatory process and their potential contributions. Following this, the tools for dissemination, including online resources, are determined.

Ecosystem management using NBS involves a unique and complex international network of stakeholders and their relationships, forming a 'transactional landscape' associated with the globally significant services provided by these ecosystems. This transactional landscape spans governments, industry (agriculture, husbandry, and tourism), scientific research, conservation non-government organizations, civil society, and international decision-making forums.

As the project is being implemented in three Mediterranean countries, a local level approach for stakeholder mapping was adopted. This approach provides an initial overview of the relevant stakeholders in the case studies of the project– both in terms of the relations between stakeholders and NBS, and directly between stakeholder groups. 30 stakeholders have been considered along with their connections in the project's case studies, encompassing regulatory, supportive and NBS services. The methodology followed by all partners in the six project case study involved identifying stakeholders for NBS and the ecosystem services they have an interest in; creating an interest-influence matrix to explore the relationship between stakeholders and NBS; organizing small virtual meetings with stakeholders for consultations.

The tools and methods that the NL4DL project produced and developed to engage stakeholders and to disseminate the results are:

- design the logo of the project;
- prepare leaflets (one with the aims and objectives and one with results of the project translated into 5 languages (English, Greek, Italian, Spanish and Catalan));
- design and print of roll ups in five languages;
- design of the project posters (7) to install in the case study sites;
- design of several scientific poster for the participation in National and International Conferences;
- creation and operation of the project web page and social media accounts;
- direct correspondence and phone calls with the stakeholders through official personalized letters;
- organization of face-to-face and virtual meetings for the presentation of the project and discussion;
- participation in sectoral fairs, events etc. (distribution of dissemination material);
- radio and local media interviews.

During the NL4DL project activities, two Living Labs were created, one in Italy and one in Spain, as "real-life" testbeds for experimentation and innovation. Each Living Lab corresponds to a cluster of stakeholders (e.g. farmers) working together at regional or sub-regional level. In addition, a Lighthouse was created in Crete, in Asterousia, to promote and scale up best practices implemented by previous projects (LIFE GIC etc). The creation of the Lighthouse is in line with the EU Mission "A Soil Deal for Europe".

3.2 Analyse and planning

3.2.1 Decision Support Web tool: description and application of the tool to identify potential Nature-Based Solutions

The [Decision Support web tool](#) (MM), elaborated and proposed by NL4DL project, is designed to guide the users, starting from the degradation processes, to identify both sustainable solutions (NBS) and indices/indicators describing the conditions and variations of each degradation process and to monitor the effectiveness of adopted solutions.

The web tool is a decision-support tool for planners and managers of PAs, accessible by web link and open to other users. The contents can also be used by students, stakeholders, professionals, or anyone has an interest in monitoring degradation processes.

A concise and exhaustive schematisation of degradation processes, covering the most recurrent ones in the Mediterranean area, has made it possible to create a scheme of connections between processes and RS and *in situ* indicators useful for monitoring the state and trends of soil and vegetation health in the relevant areas. The tool can be useful to decide and understand which categories of land degradation processes need to be prioritized. In fact, prioritisation is very often necessary due to resources and the simultaneous need for timeliness and effectiveness.

The initial Landing Page provides an overview and instructions on how to proceed. Entering the tool, the user can choose from a list of degradation processes, the most relevant ones for the area of interest. To provide a complete list and incorporate minor processes into broader categories, major degradation processes have been selected among those occurring in representative samples as that constituted by the NL4DL project pilot areas.

After selecting a degradation process, the tool will display (Figure 2) information useful to understand the phenomenon from a monitoring point of view, its implications that need to be monitored and an exhaustive list of the impacts that could be involved in the phenomenon manifestation and that should not be underestimated. In the same page are provided tabs both on indicators (RS, *in situ* and other indicators) to assess and monitor degradation phenomena, and a portfolio of NBS that can be adopted.

Fig. 2. Example of Degradation Process Tab

a. Remote Sensing indices in the MM web tool (listed in Annex B table 1)

In the MM, the RS indices considered for monitoring land degradation that can provide valuable information about the condition and health of the land are:

- Vegetation indices, such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), assess the density and vigour of vegetation cover. They measure the amount of chlorophyll present in plants and indicate their overall health and productivity. Monitoring changes in vegetation indices over time can reveal degradation, such as deforestation, desertification, or the loss of plant cover due to human activities or natural factors.
- Burned areas indices, such as the Burned Area Index (BAI) or the Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR), detect and quantify the extent of burned areas following wildfires or intentional land clearing. Monitoring the occurrence and severity of wildfires provides important insights into land degradation caused by fire, including the destruction of vegetation, loss of biodiversity, and soil degradation.
- Water indices, such as the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), help assess the presence and quality of water resources. They indicate the abundance of water in vegetation and soil, as well as the condition of water bodies. Monitoring water indices can reveal land degradation associated with water scarcity, drought, or excessive irrigation, which can lead to soil erosion, desertification, and reduced agricultural productivity.
- Soil indices, such as the Normalized Difference Soil Index (NDSI) or The Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index (NDBSI), provide information about percentage of bare soil exposed during a period of monitoring and in general can identify areas where soils are dominant over tree coverage. Monitoring soil indices can identify degradation processes such as soil erosion, nutrient depletion, soil sealing, or changes in soil structure, which affect agricultural productivity and ecosystem health.
- Soil salinity indices, such as the Normalized Difference Salinity Index (NDSI), quantify the salt content in the soil. Excessive salinity can result from poor irrigation practices or natural processes like saltwater intrusion. Monitoring soil salinity indices helps identify areas where salinization is occurring, which leads to reduced agricultural productivity, vegetation loss, and ecosystem degradation.
- Drought and dryness indices, such as the Normalized Difference Drought Index (NDDI) or the Vegetation Condition Index (VCI), measure the moisture content of vegetation and soil. They indicate the severity and duration of drought events and can help assess the impact of climate change and human activities on water availability. Monitoring drought indices provides insights into land degradation due to water stress, reduced crop yields, and increased vulnerability of ecosystems.

By monitoring these indices over time and across different regions, land managers and policymakers can identify areas experiencing degradation, understand the underlying causes, and implement appropriate measures to mitigate and reverse land degradation processes.

b. Composite Indices (listed in Annex B table 2)

Although the synthetic information of a classical RS index can be considered effective in providing information about the state of a particular environmental component, the complexity of some degradation processes requires the combined use of composite indices. Within NL4DL project, some of them were selected to investigate the possibility of using these indices within decision-making processes related to the planning of areas at risk of degradation/desertification.

In the MM, the composite indices are:

SDG 15.3.1: This Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) indicator focuses on the proportion of land that is subject to degradation, including processes such as erosion, desertification, deforestation, and loss of soil quality. It aims to measure the extent of soil erosion and desertification, which are significant forms of land degradation affecting agricultural productivity, biodiversity, and ecosystem sustainability.

SDG 15.1.2: This indicator within SDG 15 relates to the proportion of important ecosystems that are under PAs, compared to their total area. It assesses the extent to which ecosystems of high importance for biodiversity conservation are effectively protected through designated PAs, contributing to the preservation of biodiversity and sustainable land management.

SDG 11.3.1: This indicator falls under SDG 11, which focuses on sustainable cities and communities. The indicator 11.3.1 specifically measures the Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate.

ESAI (Environmentally Sensitive Areas to Desertification Index): It is a composite index that assesses the vulnerability of environmentally sensitive areas to desertification. By considering indicators such as vegetation cover, soil quality, and climatic factors, ESAI helps identify areas at risk of desertification, allowing for targeted interventions and conservation efforts to prevent or mitigate land degradation caused by desertification.

SDVI (Standardized Drought Vulnerability Index): SDVI is an index that quantifies and assesses the vulnerability of an area to drought. It combines various indicators such as precipitation, temperature, soil moisture, and vegetation health to provide a standardized measure of drought vulnerability. SDVI helps in evaluating and comparing the vulnerability of different regions to drought, enabling effective drought management strategies, resource allocation, and planning for drought-prone areas.

NDWI-1 Normalized Difference Water Index 1	In situ and other indicator for Decline in Vegetation Cover
<p>NDWI - Normalized Difference Water Index</p> <p>The Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) (Gao, 1996) is a satellite-derived index from the Near-Infrared (NIR) and Short Wave Infrared (SWIR) channels. The SWIR reflectance reflects changes in both the vegetation water content and the spongy mesophyll structure in vegetation canopies, while the NIR reflectance is affected by leaf internal structure and leaf dry matter content but not by water content. The combination of the NIR with the SWIR removes variations induced by leaf internal structure and leaf dry matter content, improving the accuracy in retrieving the vegetation water content (Ceccato et al. 2001). The amount of water available in the internal leaf structure largely controls the spectral reflectance in the SWIR interval of the electromagnetic spectrum. SWIR reflectance is therefore negatively related to leaf water content (Tucker 1980). Its usefulness for drought monitoring and early warning has been demonstrated in different studies (e.g., Gu et al. 2007; Ceccato et al. 2002). It is computed using the near infrared (NIR) and the short wave infrared (SWIR) reflectance (Eq.1), which makes it sensitive to changes in liquid water content and in spongy mesophyll of vegetation canopies (Gao, 1996 ; Ceccato et al., 2001).</p> <p>One is used to monitor changes in water content of leaves, using near-infrared (NIR) and short-wave infrared (SWIR) wavelengths, proposed by Gao in 1996.^[1]</p> $NDWI = \frac{(X_{nir} - X_{swir})}{(X_{nir} + X_{swir})}$ <p>Another is used to monitor changes related to water content in water bodies, using green and NIR wavelengths, defined by McFeeters (1996):</p> $NDWI = \frac{(X_{green} - X_{nir})}{(X_{green} + X_{nir})}$ <p>Interpretation</p> <p>Visual or digital interpretation of the output image/raster created is similar to NDVI:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -1 to 0 - Bright surface with no vegetation or water content +1 - represent water content <p>For the second variant of the NDWI, another threshold can also be found in McFeeters(1996) that avoids creating false alarms in urban areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> < 0.3 - Non-water >= 0.3 - Water. 	<p>In situ and other indicator for Decline in Vegetation Cover</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate time-series • Land surface temperature • Evapotranspiration • Land use/land cover • Biodiversity Index • Forest structure • Invasive species cover (%) • Weeds cover (%) • Land Net Primary Productivity (gC/m²/day) • Vegetation and habitat map • Phenology map • Green infrastructures • Landscape elements • Areas affected by wildfires <p>Other Indicator(s):</p> <p>SDG 15.3.1 - "proportion of land that is degraded over total land area":</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Land Cover (LC) change (Trend in LC) ▪ Loss of habitat quality ▪ Burnt Areas ▪ Fragmentation Index ▪ Areas of potential impact ▪ Density of artificial LC <p>ESA (I) - Environmentally Sensitive Areas to Desertification (Index)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Vegetation Quality Index (VQI)

Fig. 3. Example of a RS Indicator tab (on the right) and in situ and other indicators which can be used to monitor, assess and tackle the selected degradation process.

c. In situ indicators

The *in situ* indicators list includes indicators used to monitor and assess land degradation. These indicators can be categorized into physical and ecological indicators, as well as socio-economic indicators. These indicators are used to assess the state of land degradation and provide valuable information for monitoring and decision-making processes to promote sustainable land management and conservation. This type of indicators needs information on the ground, available through surveys and field measurements. Although they are time and cost expensive, they are fundamental and complementary to RS indicators. However, covering large portions of the territory is difficult, both because of the sample size sometimes required to align with exhaustive statistical reliability and because of the difficulty in reaching certain sampling points. In addition, the frequency of updating amplifies the costs and time required for subsequent processing. The choice of effective sampling schemes and suitable update frequency represents a crucial node in the application of any monitoring and degradation assessment model.

In the MM, *in situ* indicators are:

Physical and ecological Indicators:

- Climate: Indicators related to climate conditions such as air temperature, rainfall, aridity index, potential evapotranspiration, rainfall seasonality, and rainfall erosivity.
- Water: Indicators related to water resources, including water quality, water quantity, groundwater exploitation, and water consumption/demand.
- Soils: Indicators related to soil characteristics, such as drainage, parent material, slope aspect, slope gradient, soil depth, soil texture, soil water storage capacity, organic matter content, and electrical conductivity, stoniness, pH, nutrient content.

- Topography: Indicators related to elevation, aspect, slope gradient, relief, landform, watershed boundaries, microtopography and geomorphological features.²
- Vegetation: Indicators related to plant species presence, abundance, distribution and composition, vegetation cover, including major land use types, habitat types, conservation status, structure, dynamism, and deforested areas.
- Water Runoff: Indicators related to water runoff, such as drainage density, flooding frequency, and impervious surface area.
- Fires: Indicators related to fire occurrence and its impact, including fire frequency, fire risk, and burned area.

Socio-economic Indicators:

- Agriculture: Indicators related to agricultural practices and outcomes, such as farm ownership, farm size, land fragmentation, net farm income, and parallel employment.
- Cultivation: Indicators related to cultivation practices, including tillage operations, tillage depth, tillage direction, and mechanization index.
- Husbandry: Indicators related to animal husbandry practices, such as grazing control and grazing intensity.
- Land Management: Indicators related to land management practices, including fire protection, sustainable farming, reclamation of affected and mining areas, soil erosion control measures, soil water conservation measures, and the presence of terracing.
- Land Use: Indicators related to land use patterns, such as land abandonment, land use intensity, land use type, period of current land use, and distance from the seashore.
- Water Use: Indicators related to water resource management, including aquifer over-exploitation, irrigation percentage of arable land, runoff water storage, water consumption by sector, and water scarcity.
- Tourism: Indicators related to tourism activities, such as tourism intensity and tourism change.
- Social: Indicators related to social factors, including human poverty index, old age index, population density, population growth rate, and population distribution.
- Institutional: Indicators related to institutional factors, including farm subsidies, PAs, and policy implementation.

² The indicators related to topography can help in understanding the landscape's physical features, which influence water flow, soil deposition, and vegetation patterns, among other ecological processes. The topographical indicators important for identifying and implementing NBS are elevation (determines climate conditions, vegetation types, and species distribution. Higher elevations might have cooler temperatures and different species adapted to those conditions); aspect (the direction a slope faces can influence microclimate conditions, including sunlight exposure, temperature, and moisture, which in turn affects vegetation types and ecosystem processes); slope gradient (affects soil erosion rates, runoff, and water infiltration. Steeper slopes may require specific solutions to prevent erosion and promote water conservation); relief (the difference in elevation between the highest and lowest points in an area. It can influence climate patterns, water flow, and habitat diversity within the landscape); landform (identifies the physical form of the landscape (e.g., valley, plateau, mountain, plain); different landforms can suggest specific NBS, such as reforestation in valleys or sustainable grazing on plateaus); watershed boundaries (understanding the boundaries of watersheds is crucial for managing water resources, controlling runoff, and planning restoration projects that enhance water quality and availability); microtopography (small-scale variations in topography can create diverse microhabitats and influence ecosystem dynamics. Restoring or mimicking natural microtopographic features can enhance habitat heterogeneity and biodiversity); geomorphological features (features such as river terraces, alluvial fans, and glacial till plains have specific soil and hydrological characteristics, offering insights into suitable NBS for ecosystem restoration).

This list of NBS considered in the MM (collected from the restoration activities of the NL4DL case studies and listed in the Catalogue, Annex A), consists of various NBS aimed at ecological restoration, habitat restoration, ecological protection, and soil and water bioengineering. The listed NBS represent a general list of restoration solutions: the implementation of the MM may take place through the inclusion of further NBS categories to be used for the restoration of degraded areas in arid and semi-arid zones, and the identification of possible indicators to monitor their effectiveness in counteracting degradation processes.

Once the solutions have been put in place to address the degradation process, the manager/planner can reuse the tool to address a secondary or parallel problem, or even use the same monitoring approach to verify the effectiveness of the solutions adopted.

BOX 4. An example of using the web tool: Aridification

A manager of a PA can effectively address a soil degradation process, such as aridification, through a comprehensive approach that combines RS indices and *in situ* measurements, ultimately leading to the implementation of NBS.

The steps are:

1. Identification of the degradation process through biophysical evidence and information. *The evidence can be the increase of frequency of bare soil exposed during the year or the loss of vegetation cover in area of interest.*

2. Selection of RS and *in situ* indicators to evaluate the state and monitoring the evolution of aridification in the area.

*Bare soil monitoring can be effectively performed through “NDBSI - Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index” which is in the list of remote sensing indices. High values from these indices will identify bare soils in the area, from a diachronic assessment of this index a change in the state of soil can help to identify the vulnerable area. From the suggested *in situ* indicators Aridity index and Rainfall data can provide a medium-term vision of the phenomenon in the area, distinguishing historically bare soil areas from more recent ones.*

This step can be divided into two phases:

2.1 Data Analysis: process and analyse the data gathered from both RS and *in situ* measurements. This step involves the use of specialized software and algorithms to extract meaningful information, such as trends in soil moisture, changes in vegetation, and identifying areas prone to aridification.

2.2 Identification of Vulnerable Areas: based on the analysis, identify specific areas within the protected zone that are most vulnerable to soil degradation and aridification. This might involve the development of vulnerability maps.

3. Selection of Nature-based Solutions:

Design and implement NBS tailored to the identified vulnerable areas. NBS could include *reforestation, afforestation, wetland restoration, or soil conservation techniques like contour farming*. These solutions aim to restore ecosystem functions and enhance soil health naturally. The manager can choose according to the context (e.g., no agricultural activity and impossibility of afforestation given the climate regime) to use the “reestablishment of landscape features”. *Stone walls* and *windbreaks* solutions can act as physical barriers to reduce the speed of water runoff and control soil erosion. In fact, if placed strategically on slopes, they intercept rainwater, allowing it to infiltrate into the soil rather than carrying away valuable topsoil. Wind can erode topsoil and damage vegetation by removing moisture and causing physical damage. Stone walls can also act as barriers to reduce the wind's intensity, protecting the soil and plants from wind erosion. This helps prevent soil erosion, which is a major contributor to land degradation.

As said, once the solutions have been put in place, the manager/planner can reuse the tool both to address a secondary or parallel problem, and to verify the effectiveness of the solutions adopted.

3.2.2 Procedure for medium and long-term monitoring through in situ and RS data

Data management (*in situ* and RS data) is essential to understanding, planning, implementing, and monitoring ecological restoration activities. Data and information for a given project should be easy to retrieve for monitoring and reporting of project components to be effective. In addition, collection and archiving of data is critical to ensuring the success of future projects. Plans for managing data should be included during early data-gathering stages.

Due to the multiple factors driving degradation processes (e.g., soil erosion, spread of alien/invasive species, drought, or extreme climate events), natural or semi-natural ecosystems require monitoring procedures that can assess multiple spatial and temporal scales. In this context, the combination of *in situ* and RS observations, used both for context characterization and the development of spatial-temporal predictive models, proves to be the most effective way to obtain scalable monitoring procedures. This approach is suited for local monitoring, where the field surveys for collecting observations can be faced by stakeholders. It should evaluate the sub-indicators of LD for the SDG Indicator 15.3.1, suggested by the [UNCCD guidelines](#), as well as additional sub-indicators which are idiosyncratic of the studied site and its degradation process.

Predictive models for ecosystems monitoring are usually produced using supervised learning techniques, where *in situ* observations represent ground truth data (response variable) used to train models based on RS observations, such as satellite images, and ancillary data, such as climate data (predictor variables). On the other hand, unsupervised techniques such as clustering (not driven by data) can be useful for a preliminary exploration and description of collected, unlabelled observations. Because of the complexity of degradation processes, both *in situ* and RS observations should be carefully assessed and collected based on the target process to monitor and its environmental context. Multiple sources of degradation could characterise the study site, and in turn, different procedures should be adopted to monitor the different sources of degradation. Each of these procedures should consider different types of *in situ* observations and their relative predictor variables to produce reliable mathematical models for spatial and temporal predictions of ecosystem conditions. The combined evaluation of all these conditions can be used to estimate and monitor the degree of degradation.

In situ observations consist of samples of the investigated target phenomena collected within a pre-defined Area of Interest (AOI) as part of the monitoring procedure (pag. 77 of [Deliverable A2.1](#)). In *in situ* observations should be assessed according to expert-knowledge of local pressure and threats, localized by accurate coordinates. Each *in situ* observation should include measurements or estimations of the observed factor, as number or cover of alien species, water content in the soil or biotic stresses such as plant infections. It is important to consider the spatial-temporal domain of the observed phenomenon and to define the spatial frame extent by identifying the boundary of the AOI including a buffer area surrounding it.

RS data and techniques represent an essential support for the monitoring of LD status on wider areas as they allow:

- investigating even inaccessible areas that are difficult to reach without expensive *in situ* explorations and analysing phenomena at different spatial scales of detail;
- collecting the signal from the investigated target within a wide range of wavelengths, not only in the visible spectrum, highlighting properties of matter invisible to the human eye;
- acquiring repeated series imagery of the same scene to capture changes over time.

The spatial resolution of satellite observations or ancillary data should be suited to catch both the target of the monitoring procedure and the significant variability of predictors to better model the response variables. The choice of the working scale should be determined based on the level of detail needed for investigation (e.g., at single tree level or at landscape level) and should align with the spatial resolution of satellite data being considered. RS images are used as predictors of the observed phenomenon over time and space because of the continuous collection of satellite images of the Earth. The temporal frame should include a baseline identifying the onset of the degradation process. This helps in characterizing the initial status of the ecosystem and detecting the discrepancies between the initial and degraded states. Furthermore, it is important to consider the seasonal variability of the target variable throughout the year, as well as the temporal span. Another characteristic to consider when selecting satellite images is the time range of the monitored phenomenon which could need a long- or short-term monitoring. Lastly, spectral resolution determines the numbers and values of spectral intervals detected by satellite images, and in turn, their capability to detect objects. For instance, vegetation monitoring often relies on satellite images collected by sensors able of recording response in the near-infrared spectrum.

From RS data management several suggestions could be proposed:

- to meet the needs of local decision-makers, a more reliable assessment of the LD status than is possible using freely available products (e.g., [Copernicus services produced at a pan-European scale](#)) can be achieved by working on a local scale;
- it is essential to address all the investigations by choosing the most suitable indices and sub-indicators to be integrated in the calculation of SDG 15.3.1, starting from the analysis of local pressures and threats affecting the site;
- to allow a reduction of calculation complexity, it is important focusing on a specific class of LC subject to degradation;
- the [QGIS Trends.Earth plugin](#) is the current tool for the automatic calculation of SDG 15.3.1 and its main sub-indicators, but it often has problems of instability, and the customised use of its own data is not so straightforward;
- to assess not only empirical and crisp thresholds, the use of additional indices and sub-indicators in the calculation of SDG 15.3.1 needs to be better investigated: a fuzzy approach could represent higher reliability;
- some known sub-indicators would require more suitable formulations (hydroperiod, for example, would require taking into account the season (month) in which the presence of water (rain/snow) is detected during the year and its quantity);
- the availability of in situ data is essential for the validation of mappings obtained with RS techniques and many more field inspections would be necessary.

BOX 5. RS data availability and their processing

Among the available satellite images, the [LANDSAT](#) and [Sentinel-2](#) archives are the most used products for ecosystem monitoring, offering Earth observations at spatial resolutions of 30 m and 10 m, respectively, spanning from regional to local scales. These archives release open-source and pre-processed products with a revisiting timespan of 16 and 5 days, respectively, and 8 to 12 spectral bands.

The LANDSAT collection allows also long monitoring actions for the last four decades, whereas Sentinel-2 allows land monitoring starting from 2015. The spatial, temporal, and spectral resolution of such images allow detection of the major ecosystems and their variability over space and time. However, several ecosystems and their degradation processes respond to a finer scale to LANDSAT or Sentinel-2. In these cases, Very High-Resolution (VHR) products should be used, such as Pleiades' products. LANDSAT and Sentinel-2 provide ready-to-use products where image pre-processing (geometric and radiometric) is already included. The image evaluable pixels can be spectrally combined to obtain indices and indicators or their proxies to extract Essential Variables (EV) and related trend useful to characterize the landscape – e.g., forest and open vegetation, water, or bare soil (Annex B reports a list of useful indices and indicators from RS data). RS indices used as indicators are site dependent, therefore, to select the most explicative ones, a previous analysis is recommended. The analysis should consider the seasonal component, as some indicators presents strong correlations during specific periods.

Once the dataset composed of response and predictor variables has been established, an evaluation of the available algorithms is needed to ensure robust analyses – e.g., Neural Network, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, or Convolutional Neural Network. Depending on the target variable that it is necessary to model, it can perform regression analyses using numerical response variables, or classification analyses using categorical response variables. In the latter case, it is important to evaluate the distinctiveness of the categorical classes to ensure a good detection of classes by the algorithms.

The entire procedure can be limited by the availability of in situ data for training of data-driven algorithms and calibration/validation of degradation predictive models (Chapter 7 [Deliverable A2.1](#)). Field observations can be retrieved by archives collecting data from previous scientific studies, but the high specificity of local degradation processes and the needs by stakeholders of local scale monitoring requires the use of accurate and ad-hoc in situ observations, and in turn, a substantial workload. Also, the availability of suitable RS images can limit the development of the monitoring procedure, especially if it considers that several of the degradation pressures and threats could be detected only by purchasing VHR images.

Moreover, both the collection of in situ observations and the processing and analyses of satellite images require highly technical skills. The local environmental conditions and processes occurring in each different site constrain the monitoring procedure to carefully evaluate all the procedural steps, from the collection of field observations to the statistical analyses. The development of procedures for the local ecosystem monitoring will produce models and predictions that can support land management as well as serve as a baseline for scaling up the monitoring protocol to regional and national scales.

a. The NL4DL procedure for RS data management and indicator extraction

The proposed procedure³ doesn't offer site-specific solutions; instead, it has been conceived for application to any site⁴. To present the entire procedure to potentially interested end-users, such as those with advanced expertise in PAs management, a set of steps can be summarized as follows:

0. Definition of the spatial frame identifying the AOI extent:
 - a. Boundary of the Natura2000 site.
 - b. Buffer area size surrounding as following:
 - i. Case of AOI > 50 hectares size: a 5-km⁵ wide buffer area around;
 - ii. Case of AOI < 50 hectares size: a 1-km wide buffer area around.
1. Definition of the temporal frame to be monitored: setting the baseline to determine the initial status according to eventual trigger events.
2. Selection of the optical satellite images and their pre-processing level (radiometric and geometric calibration) to be considered:
 - a. Case of AOI > 50 hectares size:
 - i. Case of long-term monitoring, back in time before 2015: Landsat satellite data must be considered;
 - ii. Case of monitoring from 2015: Sentinel-2 in addition to Landsat satellite data can be considered;
 - b. Case of AOI < 50 hectares size: VHR commercial satellite data need to be considered.
3. Definition of the scale of detail: local site scale.
4. Identification of pressures and threats for the specific site by expert knowledge.
5. Identification and extraction of indices and sub-indicators for the SDG 15.3.1 evaluation, according to the main pressures and the available validation data.
6. Collecting all the available in situ data useful for validation of the sub-indicators.
7. List of LC classes according to the taxonomy selected.
8. List of the main changes of interest (from-to transitions) to be monitored.

³ In the framework of the NL4DL project, RS data and techniques have been employed at a local scale to extract EV (see Annex 2). These EV have been identified among several thematic indices based on RS observations. Furthermore, several indicators useful to characterize and monitor the LD status of each project study site, were selected according to the local pressures and threats affecting each site by considering freely available open data as much as possible (Deliverable A2.1). Interesting information about LD status has emerged and both quantitative and qualitative evaluations were possible for long-term and medium/short-term analysis for each study site ([Deliverable A2.2, 1st and 2nd release](#)).

⁴ Indeed, the six study sites of the NL4DL project, hosting a wide variety of ecosystem types (drylands, coastal, mountainous, with high or low extension, affected by specific treats causing LD), offer the opportunity for investigations in the variety of Mediterranean landscape.

⁵ In the NL4DL activities, the buffer area of 5 km around was selected according to the contents of ISPRA Guidelines for updating technical standards on environmental assessment (ISPRA, 2014). In the case of AOI < 50 hectares, as for Palo Laziale study site, the choice of 1 km for the buffer size was resulted comprehensive even because of the presence of an urban area beyond that was out of our scope.

- Integration of all indices and sub-indicators for the SDG 15.3.1 indicator computation by adopting the “One Out, All Out” criteria for each homogeneous area and identifying Positive, Stable and Negative (i.e., degraded) changes in the current monitoring period. From the rate between the total land that results degraded and the total land area the SDG 15.3.1 indicator can be evaluated as proportion (%) of degraded land (Sims et al., 2021).

BOX 6. NL4DL Procedure strength and weakness

The strength of the NL4DL procedure lies in its strong local scale characterisation:

- Starting from an accurate analysis of the main problems affecting the different types of ecosystems;
- Provisioning for local scale observations: HR or VHR satellite data in case of areas > 50 ha or < 50 hectares, respectively;
- Increase of sub-indicators to be combined to obtain SDG 15.3.1;
- Calculation of SDG 15.3.1 indicator at local scale overcoming the current Trends. Earth tool available at global scale as QGIS environment plugin;
- Usefulness for local decision-makers.

Different sources of weakness can arise in the NL4DL procedure application:

- Lack of availability of optical satellite data without cloud cover or need for considering clouds/clouds shadow masking;
- Satellite data result useless to track particular LD processes, such as the spread of an invasive species under a dense tree canopy;
- Need of tasking and purchase for VHR satellite data in case of small size study areas;
- Difficulty in the validation of indices and sub-indicators for the lack of historical ground truth data mainly in the past: in particular, this resulted for Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) or Net Primary Productivity (NPP) or their proxies in-field measures;
- Possibility to obtain several indices and sub-indicators for soil (e.g., SOC, soil salinity, etc.) only for those areas covered by bare soil or herbaceous vegetation (the presence of dense trees does not allow for observing the soil from satellite);
- Need to update the list of sub-indicators as the site change.

b. The use of RS and ground data: the dual approach procedure

The RS is a versatile tool for monitoring LD. It provides data on biophysical and socio-economic factors, impacts and mitigation measures. It supports land management decision making by providing information on indicators such as soil erosion, vegetation cover and land use change. It also supports policy making by providing up-to-date information on the extent and causes of LD and the potential for recovery. RS is well suited for quantifying SDG 15.3.1 indicators, but to define the structural and functional state of the ecosystem under study, it needs to adopt a criterion known as the dual approach, which considers the integration of top-down and bottom-up approaches.

The structural and functional aspects of a Mediterranean (and non-Mediterranean) ecosystem present spatial and temporal dynamic that vary depending on the scale used. Consequently, the definition of the state of health of an ecosystem can be quantified at several scales.

However, since ecological restoration activities are predominantly local, the quantification of the structural and functional parameters that indicate the state of health of the compartments that define the ecosystem must necessarily be carried out at a local scale.

The top-down approach uses indicators and models that are derived from global or regional assessments, such as climate change scenarios, LU/LC change models, or criteria and indicators for sustainable ecosystem management assessed by RS approaches. The bottom-up approach involves the participation of local operators in measuring, identifying, and evaluating the drivers, impacts, and responses of LD. In ecological terms, the bottom-up approach consists of obtaining and using more spatially precise data (local scale), consisting of ground measurements of biometric parameters such as gas exchange measurements (photosynthesis, conductance, and evapotranspiration) to quantify carbon and water fluxes within a forest ecosystem. Both approaches have advantages and limitations, and there is a need to integrate them in a coherent and consistent manner to enable complementarity between local and large-scale monitoring, and to gain a better understanding and prediction of large-scale environmental systems to achieve specific management outcomes.

The different spatial and temporal resolutions of satellite imagery and their relation to different spatial and temporal scales of environmental and human processes related to LD integrate a wide range of techniques such as optical, thermal, microwave and hyperspectral imaging that can capture different aspects of an ecological system, such as the gas exchange of the forest community to/from the atmosphere, while gas exchange measurements at the leaf/canopy level(s) can provide valuable information on plant productivity, stress responses and environmental interactions, although often limited by the spatial and temporal scales of the instruments and methods used.

3.3 Assess: determining the appropriate restoration objectives and associated activities

a. Develop goals and objectives

Clear and measurable goals and objectives of restoration activities are needed to identify the most appropriate solutions, ensure that all project participants have a common understanding of the project, and measure progress (see Monitoring Model 3.2.1).

Plans must clearly state (SER, 2019) the project vision and ecological and social targets, including a description of the site and the native ecosystem to be restored, and the definition of restoration model (natural (or spontaneous) regeneration; assisted regeneration; reconstruction; combined approach) (SER, 2019). Ecological and social goals including the level of ecological recovery sought (i.e., condition or state of the ecosystem attributes to be achieved). In full recovery cases, this will fully align with the reference model, whereas in partial recovery cases, this will include elements that deviate from the reference to some degree⁶. Ecological goals should quantify, where possible, the degree of the reference ecosystem attributes to be attained.

The social goals must be explicit and realistic, considering the time frame and social capital available in the area; the potential positive and/or adverse effects, for example from alteration of ecosystem structure or function on ES. Restoration can bring back ecosystem services, sustainable supplies of natural resources, but also aesthetic qualities, visitor experience values, and increased benefits from local populations and tourism (e.g. within PAs).

Objectives represent the changes and immediate outcomes needed to achieve the target and goals relative to any distinct spatial areas within the site. Objectives should be stated in terms of measurable and quantifiable indicators to assess whether the project is reaching its objectives within identified time frames.

b. Identify reference ecosystem(s) and models

A key step in assessing and identifying the problem to define the most effective solutions, is finding, and agreeing on a reference ecosystem(s). Plans should identify target native reference ecosystems and an appropriate reference model based on multiple indicators of the key ecosystem attributes (absence of threats, physical conditions, species composition, structural diversity, ecosystem function, external exchanges).

⁶ Full recovery is defined as the state or condition whereby, following restoration, all key ecosystem attributes closely resemble those of the reference model. These attributes include the absence of threats, species composition, community structure, physical conditions, ecosystem function, and external exchanges. Where lower levels of recovery are planned or occur due to resource, technical, environmental, or social constraints, recovery is referred to as partial recovery. An ecological restoration project or program should aspire to substantial recovery of the native biota and ecosystem functions (contrast with rehabilitation below). When full recovery is the goal, an important benchmark is when the ecosystem demonstrates self-organization. At this stage, if unexpected barriers or lack of species or processes take recovery off course, further restoration actions may be required to ensure that the trajectory ultimately continues toward full recovery. Once fully recovered, any ongoing activities (e.g., to maintain disturbance regimes) would be considered ecosystem maintenance or management. Specific activities, such as prescribed fire or the control of invasive species, may be used in both the restoration and maintenance phases of a project. (SER, 2019)

Importantly, reference models should be based on the specific ecosystem attributes to be recovered, and account for both ecological complexity and temporal change (i.e., the successional or equilibrium dynamics of the ecosystem). Key ecosystem attributes can be used to describe the reference ecosystem. Together these attributes contribute to overall ecosystem integrity, which arises from properties of diversity, complexity, and resilience inherent in functional native ecosystems. Given the large range of ecosystem types for which ecological restoration is needed, these attribute categories should be broad rather than prescriptive (SER, 2019).

ATTRIBUTE	DESCRIPTION
Absence of threats	Environmental conditions (including the physical and chemical conditions of soil and water, and topography) required to sustain the target ecosystem are present.
Physical conditions	Environmental conditions (including the physical and chemical conditions of soil and water, and topography) required to sustain the target ecosystem are present.
Species composition	Environmental conditions (including the physical and chemical conditions of soil and water, and topography) required to sustain the target ecosystem are present.
Structural diversity	Environmental conditions (including the physical and chemical conditions of soil and water, and topography) required to sustain the target ecosystem are present.
Ecosystem function	Appropriate levels of growth and productivity, nutrient cycling, decomposition, species interactions, and rates of disturbance.
External exchanges	The ecosystem is appropriately integrated into its larger landscape or aquatic context through abiotic and biotic flows and exchanges.

Fig. 4 Description of the key ecosystem's attributes used to characterize the reference ecosystem as well as to evaluate baseline condition, set project goals, and monitor degree of recovery (SER, 2019).

Reference models should not be used to immobilize an ecosystem at a specific point in time. An inherent property of ecosystems is that they change over time because of internal (e.g., changes in population growth rates) and external factors (e.g., physical disturbances). Reference models should be developed with an explicit focus on understanding temporal dynamics to develop feasible and relevant restoration designs that allow local species to recover, adapt, evolve, and reassemble.

Multiple reference models may be needed for a restoration project. First, large project sites or those with varied topography are likely to include a mosaic of ecosystems and their ecotones. Second, multiple or sequential references may be needed to reflect ecosystem dynamics or anticipated changes over time. Sites in successional ecosystems may be in the early phases of successional development immediately after treatment and later advance to other successional stages. For ecosystems with complex equilibrium dynamics, multiple successional pathways may exist, and multiple models may be necessary to attempt to describe different possible restoration outcomes. Such alternative states can result from changes in population densities

in environmental drivers or both in combination. Additionally, reference models may need adjustment over time based on the results of project monitoring (SER, 2019).

Deciding when an alternative reference ecosystem is appropriate is dependent on local conditions and the case for irreversibility and requires skilled ecological judgement (Fig. 7). More than one alternative reference ecosystem may be appropriate, for example, in urban and highly modified agricultural areas, and careful selection is necessary to match the local social-ecological situation. Additionally, the appearance of a site may not be a reliable indicator of restoration potential. In many cases where restoration was assumed by some to be impossible, recovery was achieved after the application of skilled and informed approaches. Where the potential for recovery is in doubt, but recovery is highly desirable, a standard approach is to conduct trial treatments on a small area for a sufficient period to determine efficacy. Trial treatments are best designed as collaborations between scientists and practitioners and can help inform the appropriate choice of an ecosystem to use as the basis for developing the reference model (SER, 2019).

BOX 7. To do list for the description of ecosystems (SER, 2019)

- Document substrate characteristics (biotic or abiotic, aquatic or terrestrial);
- List major characteristic species (representing all plant growth forms and functional groups of micro- and macrofauna, including pioneer and threatened species);
- Identify the ecosystem's functional attributes, including nutrient cycles, characteristic disturbance and flow regimes, successional pathways, plant-animal interactions, ecosystem exchanges, and any disturbance-dependence of component species;
- Note any ecological mosaics that require the use of multiple reference ecosystems on a site;
- In cases where extant ecosystems are being disturbed and then restored, preexisting intact ecosystems must be mapped in detail before disturbance occurs;
- Assess habitat needs of focal biota (including any faunal minimum ranges and responses to degradation pressures and restoration treatments).

Fig. 5. Decision tree to assist in the selection of appropriate native reference ecosystems for restoration projects (SER, 2019).

c. Ecosystem services assessment

The planning of an ecological restoration activity must consider the potential positive and/or adverse effects, for example from alteration of ecosystem structure or function. Map and assess ecosystem status and ecosystem services in the restoration process can avoid problems later, but also support the stakeholder involvement and the communication activities (see. 3.1.2 c).

The [purpose methodology of ES assessment](#) is to integrate ground data and existing thematic data layers with RS observations to account for temporal variations in ecosystem services supply regarding a baseline. The approach developed within the framework of NL4DL is tailored to tackle situations with limited or no availability of measured ground data in the case study areas (CSA) and relies on the use of existing GIS data from freely accessible web resources and RS indices at any convenient time step retrieved via [Google Earth Engine](#).

The proposed methodology⁷ allows to assess and map the values of selected ES indicators along with their relative changes with respect to the baseline years. The integration of time

⁷ In the NL4DL project, the [MAES framework](#) was taken as a reference for the assessment of ecosystems condition. [The MAES framework](#) distinguishes between indicators of environmental quality, expressing the physical and chemical quality of ecosystems (e.g. concentration of air pollutants in urban ecosystem type, or fragmentation of the other terrestrial ecosystem types), and ecosystem attributes expressing the biological quality of ecosystems. Ecosystem attributes are subdivided in structural ecosystem attributes (as General structural ecosystem attributes; Structural ecosystem attributes based on species diversity and abundance; Structural ecosystem attributes

dependent predictors from RS in a spatially explicit digital mapping workflow has allowed to visualize where the changes occur and their relative magnitudes. The presented approach proved to be sensitive enough to depict negative changes in ES supply stemming from LD processes due to different drivers acting at different scales, such as wildfires and drought, but also positive changes due to ecosystem recovery.

The approach to ES assessment and mapping can be summarised in the following methodological steps (Figure 6):

1. Identification of the target areas and of the ecosystem service(s) to be assessed and mapped at a selected resolution (e.g., above ground C stock, soil erosion control, above ground biomass);
2. Definition of a reference baseline (year) for the assessment of the target ecosystem service indicator(s);
3. Identification and retrieval of proxies (predictors, in raster format) for the assessment of indicator(s) for the targeted ecosystem service(s):
 - a. Remote sensing indicators (time dependent) over a time span of interest (e.g., weeks, months, years)
 - b. Terrain/Landscape/Soil attributes, properties, and features (time invariant);
4. Sampling over a regular grid over the target area of the predictors and target variable(s), followed by correlation analysis and calibration of regression-based algorithms to estimate the target indicator(s) over the entire area of interest at the selected raster resolution;
5. Prediction via regression of the target indicator(s) for the baseline year followed by its interval standardization (range 0-1);
6. Prediction via regression of the target indicator(s) for the time interval of interest, projecting indicator estimates ahead in time using RS indicators updates over the selected time intervals;
7. Interval standardization (0-1) of the predicted indicators over the considered timeline to assess relative changes in time with respect to the baseline year.

BOX 8. NL4DL ES assessment and mapping: Tifaracás and El Bruc (Spain), and Asterousia (Greece) case study areas

In agreement with the project partners responsible for the case study areas (CSA), the assessment in the NL4DL areas has focused so far on three ecosystem services:

- above ground C stock (AGCS),
- soil erosion control (SEC),
- above ground biomass (AGB).

The first two are regulating services, while the third is a provision service (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2018).

Given the lack of measured ground data the following were taken as proxies for the target services: i) MODIS (MOD17) net primary production (kg C m⁻², Running et al., 2004) for above ground C stock; ii) RUSLE based amount of soil mass retained by vegetation computed as the difference between potential and actual soil erosion (Mg ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, Panagos et al., 2022) for soil erosion control; and iii) Sentinel2 Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI, Rouse et al., 1974) for above ground biomass.

A different reference baseline year for ES assessment has been considered for the different areas (e.g., 2016 in Tifaracás and 2019 in El Bruc, 2015 in Asterousia), so to use RSI from the Copernicus-Sentinel2 repository which are available from 2015. The time series considered for ES assessment and mapping changes from site to site in agreement with the events that occurred and triggered land degradation processes and the possible recovery: for example, it is 2015-2022 in El Bruc and Asterousia, 2016-2022 in Tifaracás.

Using [GEE JavaScript API](#), the user can import the area of interest and select the time frame for the extraction of the required spectral bands which are further used to calculate RSI, e.g. NDVI. For each band it is possible to specify not only the time frame of interest but also the statistic relevant to the goal of the assessment. Within the NL4DL ES assessment and mapping, raster maps of yearly median values have been extracted for each CSA, using the following bands: B2 (blue), B3 (green), B4 (red), B8 (IR), B8A (IRn) and B11 (SWIR). The first four have a 10m spatial resolution, while the last two have a 20m spatial resolution. Given the different spatial resolution of the available raster layers for the three proxies, i.e. 500 m for MOD17, 100 m for soil erosion and 10m for NDVI, there was the need to rescale the first two to the desired resolution of the final maps, which was set to different resolutions depending on the size of the sites: for example it was set to 25m Tifaracás and Asterousia, and 10 m for El Bruc respectively. The downscaling resorted to stepwise multiple linear regressions (MLR) calibrated over gridded data points which were used to sample the proxies' raster layers for the selected baseline years along with several predictor variables available at the target resolutions of the final ES maps. The predictors were chosen among several RSI indices (time dependent) among those identified by action A2 of the project, and terrain, soil, and landscape attributes (time invariant) based on correlations analysis. Using the MLR calibrated for the ES proxies, it is possible to estimate them for all the other years of the time series up to 2022 using the annual median values for all the RSI predictors, and to assess relative difference with reference to the selected baselines. In the case of AGB, though, the comparison with the baseline is straightforward as the indicator is based only on NDVI which is already available at the target resolution.

Although in the case of AGB and SEC the outcomes can be expressed in terms of biophysical units, respectively Mg C ha⁻¹ and Mg ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, it is preferred to standardize the values resorting to an interval normalization. Using standardised values, it is possible to compare, and possibly map, different services or the same services across regions or over time. In this way indicator values are normalized resorting to the baseline relative scales, and range from 0 to 1, where 0 represents no relevant ecosystem service supply. Lack of relevance does not mean that a given ecosystem service is not provided but rather that its level of supply is relatively the lowest with respect to the service provided by other spatial units within a given ecosystem. At the other end of the scale, 1 represent the maximum level of ecosystem service supplied by a given ecosystem type.

From the assessment results, it can be observed that in the case of El Bruc the most relevant changes occur in 2015 and 2016, after the forest fire and again in 2022 as result of the prolonged drought that affect most of Europe. In Tifaracás, the effects of the forest fire (august 2019) have also a notable impact the loss of ES supply in 2020, but those of the 2022 drought appear to be more pronounced.

Fig. a. Relative annual variation in ES provision with reference to the selected baseline year (Left: Tifaracás, right: El Bruc).

The radar plots in Figure a eventually depict the annual variations in the three selected ESs supply with respect to the baseline years for the whole CSA. Similar analysis can be easily tailored to highlight variations on terms of ES provision for specific land use/land cover types or for administrative units, as shown in Figure b for the Spanish CSA of El Bruc.

Fig. b. Relative annual variation in ES provision with reference to the selected baseline year for different land use/land cover types in the Spanish CSA of El Bruc.

d. Cost-Benefit Analysis

Evaluating the costs and benefits associated with implementing NBS helps decision-makers make informed choices about resources allocation. Conducting a Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) (Van Zaten, 2023) for NBS involves evaluating the financial and non-financial costs and benefits associated with implementing these solutions. NBS refers to approaches that use nature and ecosystems to address various environmental and societal challenges. By thoroughly an expert assessment of costs and benefits analysis, decision-makers can make informed choices that consider the economic, environmental, and social impacts of NBS.

Here's a breakdown of the costs and benefits in a cost-benefit analysis for NBS; as in the case of CBA, analysis of the local social and economic context is fundamental, as is the involvement of local stakeholders:

Costs

- *Implementation Costs*: direct costs (expenses related to planning, designing, and executing NBS projects); indirect costs (overhead, administrative expenses, and other associated costs); Maintenance costs (regular maintenance, costs for ongoing care and management of NBS, including monitoring and adjustments); long-term maintenance (expenses for infrastructure repair or replacement over the lifespan of the project).
- *Opportunity Costs*: if the NBS involves using land that could be used for other purposes, the potential economic benefits foregone should be considered.
- *Risk Management Costs*: contingency e.g. budget for unforeseen events or challenges during implementation; insurance as costs associated with insuring against potential risks.

Benefits

- *Economic Benefits*: direct economic gains as revenue generated directly from the NBS (e.g., tourism, recreational activities); indirect economic gains as contributions to local economies through increased property values or job creation.
- *Environmental Benefits*: biodiversity enhancement as improved biodiversity and ecosystem health; climate change mitigation as contributions to carbon sequestration and climate resilience.
- *Social Benefits*: health improvements as access to green spaces contributing to improved mental and physical health; community cohesion as enhanced social connections and community well-being.
- *Cost Avoidance*: flood prevention as avoidance of costs associated with traditional flood control measures through natural floodplains; water quality as improved water quality reducing the need for expensive water treatment.

3.4 Planning and design

a. Solutions identification

The solutions should prevent expected land degradation or mitigate of ongoing land degradation or rehabilitate⁸ already degraded land (FAO, 2020). Prevention implies the employment of measures that maintain natural resources and their environmental and productive function on land, which may be at risk of degradation. Mitigation is an intervention intended to reduce ongoing degradation; this comes when degradation has already begun. The main aim here is to halt further degradation and to start improving resources and their ecosystem functions. Mitigation impacts tend to be noticeable in the short to medium term; the observed impact then provides a strong incentive for further efforts.

Rehabilitation is required when the land is already degraded to such an extent that the original use is no longer possible. In this situation, the land has become practically unproductive, and the ecosystem is seriously disturbed. Rehabilitation usually implies high investment costs with medium- to long-term benefits. (FAO, 2020)

To identify solutions that can prevent/mitigate or rehabilitate the areas starting from degradation processes, the NL4DL project built and propose a Decision Support Web Tool MM (described in section 3.2.1) to identifying a Catalogue of sustainable restoration solutions (NBS) (Annex A) as well as RS indicators and in situ indicators to monitoring the degradation processes before and after the restoration's activities.

b. Restoration solutions prescriptions

Plans should contain clearly stated solutions prescriptions for each distinct restoration area, describing what, where, and by whom treatments will be undertaken, and their order or priority. Where knowledge or experience is lacking, adaptive management or targeted research that informs appropriate prescriptions will be necessary. Plans should:

- describe actions to be undertaken to eliminate and mitigate, or adapt to causal problems;
- Identify and justify specific restoration approaches, descriptions of specific treatments for each restoration area, and prioritization of actions.

Depending on the condition of the site, this can include identification of:

- Amendments to the shape, configuration, chemistry, or other physical condition of abiotic elements to render them amenable to the recovery of target biota and ecosystem structure and functions;
- Effective and ecologically appropriate strategies and techniques to control undesirable species to protect desirable species, their habitats, and the site;
- Ecologically appropriate methods to facilitate regeneration or achieve reintroduction of any missing species;

⁸ The goal of rehabilitation projects is not native ecosystem recovery, but rather reinstating a level of ecosystem functioning for renewed and ongoing provision of ecosystem services potentially derived from nonnative ecosystems as well. Rehabilitation is one of many restorative activities aligned along a continuum that includes ecological restoration and its allied and complementary activities, all of which contribute to improving ecosystem integrity and social-ecological resilience (SER, 2019)

- Ecologically appropriate strategies to address circumstances where the ideal species or genetic stock is not immediately available (e.g., leaving gaps for in-fill reintroductions in subsequent seasons); and,
- Appropriate species selection, genetic resources, and procurement of biota to be reintroduced.

c. Assessment of site tenure security and scheduling of post-treatment maintenance

Evidence of potential for long-term conservation management of the site is required before investing in restoration (SER, 2019). Restoration plans should thus:

- Identify site-tenure security to enable long-term restoration and allow appropriate ongoing access for monitoring and management;
- Identify a plan for site maintenance after project completion to ensure that the site does not regress into a degraded state.

d. Analyze logistics

Analysis of the potential for resourcing the project and of likely risks is required before undertaking a restoration plan. To address practical constraints and opportunities, plans should:

- Identify funding, labor (including appropriate skill level), and other resources that will enable appropriate treatments (including follow-up treatments and monitoring), until the site reaches a stabilized condition;
- Undertake a full risk assessment and identify a risk-management strategy for the project, particularly including contingency arrangements for unexpected changes in environmental conditions, financing, or human resourcing;
- Develop a project timetable and rationale for the duration of the project (e.g., using a schedule planning chart);
- Identify ways to maintain commitment to the project's targets, goals, and objectives over the life of the project, including political and financial support; and,
- Obtain permissions and permits and address legal constraints applying to the site and the project, including land-tenure and ownership claims.

e. Establish a process for project review

Plans include a schedule and time frame to:

- Carry out stakeholder and independent peer review as required;
- Implement plan review considering new knowledge, changing environmental conditions, and lessons learned.

3. 5 Implement and monitor

The implementation phase may be short or long, depending on the project and circumstances. Monitoring and adaptive management may dictate restoration interventions after an initial project or stage has been completed.

During the implementation phase, restoration projects are managed to (SER, 2019):

a. Protect the site from damage

No further or lasting damage is caused by the restoration works to any natural resources or elements of the terrestrial or aquatic area impacted by the project, including physical damage (e.g., clearing, burying topsoil, trampling), chemical contamination (e.g., over-fertilizing, pesticide spills) or biological contamination (e.g., introduction of invasive species including undesirable pathogens).

b. Engage appropriate participants

Treatments are interpreted and carried out responsibly, effectively, and efficiently by, or under the supervision of, suitably qualified, skilled, and experienced people. Wherever possible, stakeholders and community members, defined in the previous step (pages 18/20), are invited to participate in project implementation. Where possible, the use of sustainable materials and processes are incorporated into restoration process.

c. Incorporate natural processes

All treatments are undertaken in a manner that is responsive to natural processes, and that fosters and protects potential for natural and assisted recovery. Primary treatments including substrate and hydrological amendments, pest animal and plant control, application of specific recovery activities, and biotic reintroductions adequately followed up by secondary treatments as required. Because the recovery period may be long (e.g., growth of riparian vegetation), interim treatments to reduce adverse effects (e.g., nutrient influxes and sediment inflows into streams) should be planned for and implemented. Appropriate aftercare is provided to any plantings or animal stock.

d. Respond to changes occurring on site

Adaptive management is applied, informed by the results of monitoring. This includes both corrective changes of direction to adapt to unexpected ecosystem responses and additional work as needed. In some cases, additional or new research may be required to overcome restoration impediments.

e. Ensure compliance

All projects exercise full compliance with work, health, and safety legislation. All laws, regulations, and permits that apply to the project, including those related to soil, air, water, oceans, heritage, species, and ecosystem conservation, are in place.

f. Communicate with stakeholders

All project staff will communicate regularly with key stakeholders through a communication plan and activities as described above, integrated with any stakeholder engagement and citizen science activities to keep stakeholders informed and engaged. Communication should also meet the requirements of funding bodies.

Ecological restoration projects adopt the principle of observing, recording, and monitoring treatments and responses to determine whether a project is on track to meeting targets, goals, and objectives, or needs adjustment. Projects are regularly assessed, with progress analysed to adjust treatments as required (i.e., using an adaptive-management framework). Collaborations are fostered between researchers, local-knowledge experts, practitioners, and citizen-scientists, especially where treatments are innovative or being applied at a large scale. Monitoring needs are reassessed throughout the project and resources are reallocated or expanded accordingly. (SER, 2019)

a. Design the monitoring process

As mentioned before (3.2.1), monitoring to evaluate restoration outcomes begins at the planning stage by developing a monitoring process to identify treatment effectiveness. This plan should include specific questions to be addressed through monitoring, sampling design for collecting baseline, implementation, and post-treatment data, procedures for documenting and archiving collected data, plans for data analysis, and plans for communicating results to adapt management strategies on site and inform stakeholders of lessons learned.

Monitoring is geared to specific targets and measurable goals and objectives identified at the start of the process. Once the degradation process and the indicators are determined, baseline data are collected, and milestones are determined to gauge whether the rate of progress is on track. Additionally, “trigger points” along that path can be helpful: if the data reaches a trigger, then corrective actions may be needed. Monitoring methods should be appropriate to the goals of the project. Whenever possible, methods should be easy-to-use, and implemented through participatory processes. When formal quantitative sampling is needed, the sampling design must include a sufficiently large sample size to enable statistical analyses and inferences. In all cases the methods should be detailed enough to be repeatable in future years.

b. Keep records

Adequate and secure records of all project data, including documents related to planning, implementation, monitoring, and reporting are maintained to inform adaptive management and enable future evaluation of responses to treatments. All treatment data, including details of restoration activities, number of work session and costs, along with all evaluation monitoring records are maintained for future reference. Provenance data should include location (preferably GPS-derived) and description of donor and receiving sites or populations. Documentation should include reference to collection protocols, date of acquisition, identification procedures, and collector/propagator’s name. Additionally:

- Consideration should be given to having data be open-access, or adding results to open-access repositories;
- Managers should archive data using secure storage. Metadata describing the contents of each dataset should be included.

c. Evaluate outcomes

Evaluation of the outcomes of the work is carried out, with progress assessed against project targets, goals, and objectives. This requires the use of the evaluation tool to adequately assess results from the monitoring. - Results should be used to inform ongoing management.

d. Report to interested parties

Reporting involves preparing and disseminating progress reports that detail evaluation results for key stakeholders and broader interest groups (e.g., in newsletters and scientific journals) to convey outputs and outcomes as they become available. Reporting should convey the information accurately and accessibly, customized to the audience, and specify the level and details of monitoring upon which any evaluation of progress has been based.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

Identify and describe

1. The problem statement is a key component of the restoration process: in fact, if defined with sufficient precision, the problem statement will also help define the necessary responses and the monitoring requirements needed to assess the effectiveness of the solutions.
2. The baseline inventory should document the causes, intensity, and extent of degradation, and describe the effects of degradation on the biota and physical environment in relation to ecosystem attributes such as absence of threats, physical conditions, species composition, structural diversity, ecosystem function, external exchanges.
3. A thorough review of all local, regional, and international conservation strategies, goals, programmes, and policies will help determine the timing of the restoration process.
4. The best way to involve stakeholders and support effective sharing is through direct contact.

Analyse and planning

1. The Decision Support Web Tool can be useful in deciding and understanding which categories of land degradation processes need to be prioritised. In fact, prioritisation is often necessary due to limited resources and the simultaneous need for timeliness and effectiveness.
2. The information for the management data should be included and analysed in the early stages of data collection.
3. Due to the complexity of degradation processes, both in situ and satellite observations should be carefully assessed and collected based on the target process to be monitored and its environmental context.
4. The working scale should be chosen based on the level of detail required for investigation. This could be at the single tree level or at the landscape level and should align with the spatial resolution of the satellite data being considered.
5. For the validation of mappings obtained with remote sensing techniques, in situ data availability is essential. Additionally, field inspections may be necessary. The collection of in situ observations, processing, and analysis of satellite images require highly technical skills.
6. To define the structural and functional state of the ecosystem under study, a *dual approach* is necessary; this approach should integrate both top-down and bottom-up approaches.

Assess

1. The restoration plans should clearly outline the vision for the restoration process, as well as the ecological and social targets.
2. Social goals should be explicit, realistic, and consider the available social capital and time frame in the area.

3. Ecosystem reference models should focus on understanding temporal dynamics to develop feasible restoration designs that allow local species to recover, adapt, evolve, and reassemble.
4. Mapping and assessing the status of the ecosystem and its services during the restoration process can prevent future issues and support stakeholder involvement and communication activities.

Design

1. Plans should contain clearly stated solutions prescriptions for each distinct restoration area, describing what, where, and by whom treatments will be undertaken, and their order or priority.
2. Evidence of potential for long-term conservation management of the site is required before investing in restoration.
3. Identify a plan for site maintenance after project completion to ensure that the site does not regress into a degraded state.
4. Identify funding, labour (including appropriate skill level), and other resources that will enable appropriate treatments (including follow-up treatments and monitoring), until the site reaches a stabilized condition.
5. Obtain permissions and permits and address legal constraints applying to the site and the project, including land-tenure and ownership claims.

Implement and monitor

1. Treatments should be carried out responsibly, effectively, and efficiently by suitably qualified, skilled, and experienced individuals or under their supervision. Whenever feasible, project implementation should involve stakeholders and community members.
2. All treatments are carried out in a way that is responsive to natural processes and promotes the potential for natural and assisted recovery. Primary treatments, such as substrate and hydrological amendments, pest animal and plant control, specific recovery activities, and biotic reintroductions, are adequately followed up by secondary treatments as necessary.
3. Project managers must ensure that monitoring is carried out to determine whether goals are met and to provide learning and adaptive opportunities.
4. Involving stakeholders in project design, data collection, and analysis can improve collaborative decision-making, provide a sense of ownership and engagement, motivate stakeholders to maintain longer-term interests, and strengthen stakeholder capacity and empowerment.

5. ANNEXES

- A. Catalogue of Actions of restoration NBS for degraded soils
- B. Catalogue of Indicators/index analysed in NL4DL project (from A3)

ANNEX A - Catalogue of Nature-based Solutions to restore areas with degraded soils

From <https://sites.google.com/view/newlifefordrylands/home-page>

Name	Solutions for Ecological Restoration (functional and/or structural)
Description	Ecological restoration involves aiding the recovery of a degraded, damaged, or destroyed ecosystem.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Food security; Human health; Natural disasters; Social and economic development; Water security.
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Aridification Change in groundwater level / quality Decline in vegetation community functioning Habitat loss Hydrological modification Increase in invasive species Increase in weeds Landscape modification Overgrazing Soil erosion by water and wind Soil organic matter decline Soil salinization Trees encroachment
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures;

	<p>Land enclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.</p>
<p>Examples</p>	<p>The Society for Ecological Restoration (SER) is a dynamic global network of over 5,000 members from 100+ countries. The SER provides, among other things, the access to a Restoration Resource Center (RRC), an interactive platform for knowledge exchange and learning in the field of ecological restoration. The RRC offers a searchable database of restoration projects and solutions from around the world. It serves as a resource for practitioners, researchers, educators, students, and the public. The projects on the SER website have been contributed by users or compiled from publicly available information by SER staff or designees.</p> <div data-bbox="422 896 1085 1456" style="background-color: #f0f0f0; padding: 10px;"> <p>Actions to restore habitats of community interest in the SAC Muela de Cortes y El Caroché</p> <p>Country: Spain</p> <p>Activities:</p> <p>Biomes:</p> <p>Abstract: SAC Muela de Cortes y El Caroché is a hotspot of biodiversity and provides a wide range of ecosystem services, as it is one of the most extensive semi-natural areas of the Valencian Community. However, this area has experienced recurrent wildfires in recent decades, including large wildfires. Rural abandonment has also contributed to landscape homogenization, and the dominance of woody communities. This project aims to develop a mosaic landscape with shrub formations, dry grasslands, and grasslands to allow the recovery of ecological interactions, ecosystem functionality and biodiversity, and protect habitats of interest. The wide diversity of actions planned aim to (i) reduce the continuity of vegetation to prevent large fires, increasing forest resistance and resilience to forest fires, (ii) increase ecosystem resistance and resilience to climate change and drought, (iii) increase the surface area of suitable habitat for large wild herbivores, (iv) meet specific objectives in relation to biodiversity, fire prevention, recovery of agricultural uses and hunting. The mosaic will also contribute to soil stabilization, regulate the hydrological cycle, stabilize carbon and nutrients, protect biodiversity, including pollinators, and increase the extent of quality pastures for wild ungulates.</p> </div> <div data-bbox="1129 902 1417 1115" style="float: right;"> </div> <div data-bbox="1129 1137 1417 1182" style="float: right;"> <p><i>Figure 1. Cleared shrubland in Muela de Cortes y El Caroché ZEC.</i></p> </div>

Name	<u>Solutions for Ecological Protection</u>
Description	Ecosystem conservation involves measures and actions to protect and maintain the integrity of natural habitats, species, and ecological processes. This includes strategies and practices to mitigate threats and minimize negative impacts.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Food security; Human health; Natural disasters; Social and economic development; Water security
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Aridification Change in groundwater level / quality Decline in vegetation community functioning Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass Habitat loss Hydrological modification Increase in invasive species Increase in weeds Landscape modification Overgrazing Soil erosion by water and wind Soil organic matter decline Soil salinization Trees encroachment
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land enclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture;

	<p>Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans</p>
<p>Examples</p>	<p>Places Nature Conservancy protects: The Atlantic Forest in Brazil</p> <p>The Nature Conservancy is a worldwide environmental non-profit organization that aims to promote a world where both people and nature can thrive. Since 1991, The Nature Conservancy has been working with various partners to protect and restore the Atlantic Forest. Their goal was to safeguard and restore 30 million acres of this magnificent forest by 2015.</p>

Name	Protected areas
Description	Protected areas, also known as conservation areas, are designated locations that receive protection due to their recognised natural, ecological, or cultural values.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Social and economic development
Ecosystem** *	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Change in groundwater level / quality Decline in vegetation community functioning Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass Increase in invasive species Increase in weeds Soil surface compaction Trees encroachment
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.
Examples	The EU's Natura 2000 network and the Bern Convention's Emerald Network are ecological networks of protected areas, set up to ensure the survival of Europe's most valuable species and habitats.

Name	<u>Land exclosures</u>
Description	Land exclosures involve fencing off an area of land to prevent human or livestock access. This practice effectively limits land degradation and improves soil health.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Natural disasters; Social and economic development; Water security
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	<u>Aridification</u> <u>Change in groundwater level / quality</u> <u>Decline in vegetation community functioning</u> <u>Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass</u> <u>Habitat loss</u> <u>Increase in invasive species</u> <u>Increase in weeds</u> <u>Soil surface compaction</u> <u>Trees encroachment</u>
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.
Examples	Since the 1990s, community-led watershed development activities in Ethiopia have included the establishment of exclosures, which are areas where both livestock and farming activities are excluded, on

degraded communal grazing land. The results of these activities demonstrate that after 16 years, exclosures can increase soil organic carbon and total soil nitrogen by an effect size greater than two. The study suggests that when planning and implementing exclosures on degraded communal grazing land, soil type and agroecology should be considered. The findings provide baseline information for future exclosure expansion and guide implementation focus. They also establish criteria for restoring soil carbon and nitrogen through exclosure planning and establishment.

Reference: Yakob G., Smith J.U., Nayak D.R., Hallett P.D., Phimister E. and Mekuria W., 2022. *Changes in Soil Properties Following the Establishment of Exclosures in Ethiopia: A Meta-Analysis*. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* 10:823026. doi: 10.3389/fevo.2022.823026

Name	Reserves, conservancies
Description	Reserves and conservancies can play a crucial role in limiting land degradation and promoting sustainable land use practices.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Social and economic development.
Ecosystem** *	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Aridification Change in groundwater level / quality Decline in vegetation community functioning Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass Habitat loss Hydrological modification Increase in invasive species Increase in weeds Landscape modification Trees encroachment
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.
Examples	The Biosphere Reserve of Białowieża in Poland is mostly covered by oak-lime-hornbeam forest Tilio-Carpinetum, which is a highly valuable forest habitat for nature protection in the temperate zone. Most of the forest habitats on both sides of the border are protected by law and exhibit a

primeval character, giving the BR exceptional value. In addition, the dead wood found in each habitat type provides a unique microhabitat for many endangered, threatened, or rare species. Although there is a relatively good understanding of the biological diversity of Europe, new species of fungi or invertebrate fauna are discovered in the Białowieża Forest almost every year.

Name	<u>Natural Systems Agriculture</u>
Description	Regenerative agriculture is an approach that integrates natural processes and principles into agricultural systems to enhance sustainability, biodiversity, and ecosystem services while promoting productive and resilient practices.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific: Agriculture
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Food security; Human health; Social and economic development; Water security.
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	<u>Aridification</u> <u>Change in groundwater level / quality</u> <u>Decline in vegetation community functioning</u> <u>Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass</u> <u>Habitat loss</u> <u>Increase in invasive species</u> <u>Increase in weeds</u> <u>Landscape modification</u> <u>Overgrazing</u> <u>Soil erosion by water and wind</u> <u>Soil organic matter decline</u> <u>Soil salinization</u> <u>Soil surface compaction</u> <u>Trees encroachment</u>
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed

	<p>rewilding; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.</p>
<p>Examples</p>	<p>The Land Institute breeds new perennial grain and seed crops adapted to ecologically intensified polycultures that mimic natural systems, known as Natural Systems Agriculture. This aims to develop an agricultural system that can produce ample food, reduce or eliminate impacts from the disruptions and dependencies of industrial agriculture, and inform cultural change through education.</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="width: 45%;"> <p>Ecosphere Studies Ecosphere Studies extends The Land Institute's innovative work in Natural Systems Agriculture to educational and cultural transformation.</p> </div> </div>

Name	Agro-ecology/Regenerative agriculture
Description	Agroecology is a farming approach that prioritises ecological principles such as diversity, synergy, and resilience. It can significantly limit land degradation by promoting sustainable land use practices and reducing the negative impact of agricultural activities on the environment.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific: Agriculture
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Food security; Human health; Social and economic development; Water security.
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Aridification Change in groundwater level / quality Decline in vegetation community functioning Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass Habitat loss Increase in invasive species Increase in weeds Soil organic matter decline Soil surface compaction Trees encroachment
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil

	and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.
Examples	Barilla and Davines will compare sustainable agriculture techniques with regenerative agriculture as part of the “Bello e Buono” programme . The project aims to measure the impact of different agricultural practices on soil fertility and biodiversity by increasing organic matter. It will also evaluate the economic impact of crop cultivation across various supply chains on a farm. The agreement emphasises the strong connection between regenerating the soil through agricultural practices and improving the health of people who benefit from a healthier diet and cosmetic benefits. Additionally, the project aims to promote regenerative practices in cultivating local crops. To speed up the process towards responsible land use and increase biodiversity, it is essential to empower farmers, disseminate a universal culture, and establish unanimous consensus on the practices to be adopted.

Name	Organic farming
Description	Organic farming aims to produce food in an environmentally sustainable way by promoting the use of regenerative practices that preserve soil health and biodiversity, limiting land degradation.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific: Agriculture
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Food security; Human health; Social and economic development
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Aridification Change in groundwater level / quality Decline in vegetation community functioning Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass Habitat loss Increase in invasive species Increase in weeds Soil organic matter decline
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.
Examples	Organic farming will play an essential role in developing a sustainable food system for the EU by producing high-quality food with low environmental impact. In 2021, the European Commission adopted

an action plan to support the target of having at least 25% of the EU's agricultural land under organic farming and a significant increase in organic aquaculture by 2030, as set out in the Farm to Fork strategy and the Biodiversity strategy. In this context, Member States were requested to establish national target values for organic farming as a percentage of total UAA by 2030. They were also encouraged to be ambitious in promoting organic production in their CAP strategic plans and national organic action plans.

France, Spain, Italy, and Germany are the four EU countries with the largest area under organic farming, accounting for 52% of the total in 2012 and 59% in 2020.

Name	<u>Agroforestry</u>
Description	Agroforestry is a system of land use management that combines tree cultivation with crops and/or livestock to create synergies and benefits for both the environment and farmers.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific: Agriculture
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Social and economic development.
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	<u>Decline in vegetation community functioning</u> <u>Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass</u> <u>Habitat loss</u> <u>Increase in invasive species</u> <u>Increase in weeds</u> <u>Soil organic matter decline</u> <u>Trees encroachment</u>
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.
Examples	<u>Agroforestry</u> is an ancient agricultural practice that is still widely used in certain EU countries. It is gaining renewed interest due to its many economic and environmental benefits. Agroforestry is a dynamic system that combines trees, crops, and/or livestock on the same area of land in some form of spatial arrangement or

temporal sequence. Prominent examples of agroforestry systems include the dehesa ecosystem in Spain, where oak trees are grown alongside livestock grazing, and the Fennoscandian area, which covers Finland, Norway, and Sweden, as well as a part of Russia, and is known for its practice of reindeer husbandry.

Table 1 – Key agroforestry practices in some European countries, by system, country and area covered

System	Country	Extent (hectares)	
Mediterranean oak tree agroforestry	Dehesa in Spain	3 606 151	
	Montado in Portugal	1 059 000	
	Grazed woodlands and oak and other agroforestry on agricultural land in Greece	1 895 583	
	Pyrenean oak (<i>Quercus pyrenaica</i>) in Spain and Portugal	122 000	
	Grazed oak woodlands in Italy	279 263	
	Sub-total	6 961 997	
Other wood pastures and meadows	<i>Larix decidua</i> (European larch) in Italy	102 319	
	Lövängar, hagmarker in Sweden	100 000	
	Other parkland, woodland, wood-pasture, <i>Hudewald</i> , <i>Haka</i> and <i>metsälaidun</i> in the UK, Germany, Austria, Switzerland, Hungary, Finland	200 320	
	Sub-total	402 639	
Reindeer husbandry	Finland, Sweden, Norway	41 400 000	
Hedges and scattered trees	France and parts of the UK and Belgium	472 074	
Agroforestry with fruit trees	Germany, Switzerland, Austria, Romania, Croatia, Czechia, France, the UK, Denmark, Italy, Greece, Poland, Portugal	1 226 867	
	with olives	Portugal, Greece, France, Italy and Spain	538 865
	with pine-trees	Italy and Portugal	535 842
	with vines	Italy, Spain and Portugal	275 635
	with chestnuts	Portugal, France, Italy, Greece, Hungary, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Switzerland	111 083
	with carob trees	Italy, Portugal, Spain and Greece	92 200
	Sub-total	2 780 492	
	Shelterbelts (windbreaks)	Hungary	16 415
Alley cropping	France	6 300	
Trees with livestock	Netherlands	3 000	
Total		52 042 917	
Total (excluding reindeer)		10 642 917	

Source: [Agforward](#) project, Stratification of agroforestry.

Name	Evolutionary-orientated forestry
Description	Evolutionary-oriented forestry aims to replicate natural forest ecosystems and processes. The approach prioritises creating diverse, resilient, and adaptable forests that can withstand environmental stressors while maintaining their ecological integrity.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Natural disasters; Social and economic development
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Decline in vegetation community functioning Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass Habitat loss Increase in invasive species Increase in weeds Soil organic matter decline Trees encroachment
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.
Examples	Adapting to climate change is crucial in forest management. While forest tree populations have a significant adaptive capacity, it is not unlimited. Integrating evolutionary factors into adaptive forestry

practices can improve the ability of managed forests to respond to climate-driven changes.

Evolution-oriented forestry

Table 1 Some examples of evolution-oriented forestry practice, including re-orientation of usual interventions (no supplementary cost) and additional interventions

Forestry practice	Expected benefits	Associated costs and risks
N_e -oriented regulation of the density and spatial distribution to equalize reproductive success between trees in small populations	Reduce the variance in reproductive success to reduce genetic drift Reduce spatial genetic structure in the seedlings and inbreeding in next generation	No supplementary cost Risk to slow down the elimination of detrimental genes, prefer equalization of mating success per patch (compatible with the next line)
In heterogeneous environment, dissociate areas of production and areas of evolution (selection patches in harsh areas) and allow gene flow between these entities	Increase the reproductive contribution of the trees that have survived to drastic selection pressure	Limited supplementary cost Requires preliminary simulation studies to estimate benefits in various contexts (strength and spatial structure of the environmental heterogeneity)
Save the lone tree, which cumulates long distance dispersal (in allo-pollinated seeds) and can be adapted to marginal conditions; collect seeds for local assisted regeneration	Diversify the mating pairs to favour the emergence of new genotypic combinations Promote adaptation to marginal conditions	Limited supplementary cost Requires a protocol for assisted regeneration Risk of inbreeding if self-pollinated seeds are not purged at a very early stage (e.g. seed abortion)
Assisted local seed dispersal (e.g. collecting, possibly over several years, mixing and replanting seeds within the stand) or pollen dispersal (e.g. air flow used in seed orchards)	Enhance local gene flow to diversify the mating pairs and favour the emergence of new genotypic combinations Reduce inbreeding	Potentially significant supplementary cost Requires preliminary studies to estimate benefits in various contexts (genetic diversity and spatial structure) Requires a protocol for assisted regeneration
Enhance local migration capacity by favouring seed dispersal and germination at distance from the main stand	Speed-up colonisation of locally favourable habitats in an environmental gradient	Potentially significant supplementary cost
Genetic enrichment by introduction of a limited amount of seeds or pollen from presumably pre-adapted allochthonous origins	Introduce pre-adapted genotypes Increase local genetic diversity	Potentially significant supplementary cost Risk of gene swamping and reduction of effective population size (N_e) if local population is small and if introduced material has low genetic diversity Risk of unforeseen local maladaptation
Marker-assisted selective thinning (futurist)	Increase selection intensity on target major genes while retaining genetic diversity in the rest of the genome	High supplementary cost Requires accurate genetic knowledge and high-throughput genotyping capacities

Reference: Lefèvre F., Boivin T., Bontemps A. et al., 2014. *Considering evolutionary processes in adaptive forestry*. Annals of Forest Science 71, 723–739 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-013-0272-1>

Name	Ecosystem-based management
Description	Ecosystem-based management aims to maintain and restore ecosystem health by considering interactions between the environment, natural resources, and human activities.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Food security; Social and economic development; Water security
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Aridification Change in groundwater level / quality Decline in vegetation community functioning Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass Habitat loss Increase in invasive species Increase in weeds Soil organic matter decline Soil surface compaction Trees encroachment
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land enclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.

Examples

Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM) is a suitable approach for managing kelp forests. Case studies of kelp forest management are ongoing in British Columbia (Canada), California (United States), and northern Chile.

Reference: Hamilton S.L., Gleason M.G., Godoy N., Eddy N., Grorud-Colvert K., 2022. *Ecosystem-based management for kelp forest ecosystems*. Mar. Policy, 136 (2022), Article 104919, 10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104919

Name	Ecosystem-based fire management strategies
Description	Ecosystem-based fire management aims to maintain and improve ecosystem health while reducing the risk of uncontrolled wildfires.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific: Fire
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Human health; Natural disasters
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	<u>Habitat loss</u>
NBS correlated	Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Reserves, conservancies
Examples	<u>Fire management plans</u> aim to prevent fires, protect people, property and forests from fire events, and use fire to accomplish forest management and other land-use objectives for a specific area. An effective fire management programme must consider the ecology and fire history of the area, as well as knowledge of fire regimes, probable fire effects, values at risk, level of forest protection required, cost of fire-related activities, and prescribed fire technology.

Global Early Warning System for Wildland Fire
Mapping Products

Note: Since 23 February 2021 the GFEWS is offline - it will be reactivated as financial support will be identified.
Click on the map for the GFMC Early Warning Portal

Global Fire EWS 10-day forecasts

Global FWI Monthly Forecasts

Name	<u>Managed rewilding</u>
Description	Managed rewilding involves restoring ecosystems and allowing natural processes to take place with minimal human intervention. Its aim is to reverse land degradation by reintroducing native species, recreating habitats, and promoting ecological balance.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Natural disasters.
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	<u>Decline in vegetation community functioning</u> <u>Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass</u> <u>Habitat loss</u> <u>Increase in invasive species</u> <u>Increase in weeds</u> <u>Landscape modification</u> <u>Overgrazing</u> <u>Soil erosion by water and wind</u> <u>Soil organic matter decline</u> <u>Trees encroachment</u>
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.

Examples

[Rewilding Europe](#) is a pan-European organization with a central team and landscape teams that are closely linked and work together.

Establishing coexistence corridors

Boosting Marsican brown bear numbers

Restoring the scavengers

Return of the Iberian Lynx

Name	<u>Trapping sediment with vegetation measures</u>
Description	Using vegetation to trap sediment is an effective way to limit and prevent land degradation, especially in areas prone to soil erosion. Vegetation stabilizes soil, reduces water runoff velocity, and traps sediment, making it crucial in preventing erosion.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Natural disasters
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	<u>Change in groundwater level / quality</u> <u>Hydrological modification</u> <u>Landscape modification</u> <u>Overgrazing</u> <u>Soil erosion by water and wind</u> <u>Soil organic matter decline</u> <u>Soil surface compaction</u>
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land enclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Water and forest management plans.
Examples	The <u>paper</u> extensively reviews scientific journal articles, case studies, and reports that assess soil conservation efforts in various environmental situations and the efficacy of vegetative and structural measures in trapping sediment.

Mekonnen M., Keesstra S. D., Stroosnijder L., Baartman J. E. M. & Maroulis J., 2015. [*Soil conservation through sediment trapping: A review.*](#) Land Degradation & Development 26, 544–556.

Name	<u>Soil and water Bioengineering</u>
Description	Soil and water bioengineering involves using living plants and organic materials to prevent or reduce land degradation and erosion. This approach utilises the natural properties of vegetation and other biological materials to stabilise soil, regulate water flow, and restore degraded landscapes.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Natural disasters; Water security
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Change in groundwater level / quality Hydrological modification Landscape modification Overgrazing Soil erosion by water and wind Soil salinization Soil surface compaction
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plans.
Examples	The work compares the definitions of Soil and Water Bioengineering, NBS, and other terminologies related to the NBS concept.

Reference: Preti F., Capobianco V., Sangalli P., 2022. [*Soil and Water Bioengineering \(SWB\) is and has always been a nature-based solution \(NBS\): A reasoned comparison of terms and definitions*](#). Ecol. Engin 2022, 181, 106687.

Examples of soil-bioengineering solutions for soil erosion and bank stabilization in different climatic areas, reported in the article are:

- a) SWB construction at La Nueva Concepción (Guatemala) single walled crib wall at the base and living branches at the slope;
- b) Live pole drains and lateral drain fascines along a slope in Walker's Landing Road, British Columbia, Canada;
- c) Prefabricated wooden structure for reinforcement of a reshaped slope in Italy (photo: F. Preti);
- d) Embankment in Southern Brazil before and after the implementation of reinforcement works.

Name	<u>Water and forest management plans</u>
Description	Water and forest management plans are essential in limiting and preventing land degradation. They aim to ensure the sustainable use and conservation of water resources and forests, which are interconnected with land ecosystems.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Natural disasters; Social and economic development; Water security.
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	<u>Hydrological modification</u> <u>Landscape modification</u> <u>Overgrazing</u> <u>Soil erosion by water and wind</u> <u>Soil salinization</u> <u>Trees encroachment</u>
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land enclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures
Examples	The FAO publication “A <u>Guide to Forest-Water Management</u> ” is a comprehensive global guide on monitoring, managing, and valuing forest-water interactions. It uses specific forest ecosystem types as examples to illustrate how sustainable forest management can support hydrologic functions and services at different scales, from local to landscape.

A woman unloading mangrove logs that will be used for charcoal production

Name	<u>(Elements of) Green Infrastructures</u>
Description	Green infrastructure uses natural systems and processes to provide environmental, social, and economic benefits. It integrates natural features and processes into the planning, design, and management of human-made infrastructure.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Human health; Natural disasters; Social and economic development; Water security
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	<u>Change in groundwater level / quality</u> <u>Decline in vegetation community functioning</u> <u>Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass</u> <u>Habitat loss</u> <u>Hydrological modification</u> <u>Increase in invasive species</u> <u>Increase in weeds</u> <u>Landscape modification</u> <u>Soil erosion by water and wind</u> <u>Soil organic matter decline</u> <u>Soil salinization</u> <u>Soil surface compaction</u> <u>Trees encroachment</u>
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas;

	<p>Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plan.</p>
<p>Example</p>	<p>The Life PollinAction Project aims to support plants and pollinators by creating a Green Infrastructure. This infrastructure is a network of habitats, including small woodlands, hedges, and meadows, where plants and animals can spread, move around, seek shelter, and find the resources they need to survive. By bringing nature back into our urban and rural areas, we can benefit wildlife while improving our quality of life.</p> <p>Shrub assemblages</p>

Name	<u>Afforestation of former grasslands</u>
Description	Afforestation involves planting trees and establishing forests on land that was previously covered by grass or used for non-forest purposes.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Social and economic development; Water security
Ecosystem** *	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	<u>Aridification</u> <u>Hydrological modification</u> <u>Increase in invasive species</u> <u>Increase in weeds</u> <u>Landscape modification</u> <u>Overgrazing</u> <u>Soil erosion by water and wind</u> <u>Trees encroachment</u>
NBS correlated	Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plan
Examples	Afforestation can improve hydrological processes, such as infiltration, in basins. This can reduce the impact of floods, soil erosion, landslides, droughts, and climate variation on human populations. The aim of this work was to analyse how afforestation and other changes in land use influence infiltrability and soil evolution.

Mongil-Manso J., Navarro-Hevia J., San Martín R., 2022. [Impact of Land Use Change and Afforestation on Soil Properties in a Mediterranean Mountain Area of Central Spain](#). Land 2022, 11, 1043.

Name	<u>Constructed wetlands</u>
Description	Constructed wetlands are natural solutions used to limit, halt, and restore degraded land. They involve creating or restoring wetland ecosystems using engineered techniques.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Water security
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Change in groundwater level / quality Habitat loss Increase in invasive species Increase in weeds Landscape modification Overgrazing Soil organic matter decline Soil salinization
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plan.
Examples	A French constructed wetland (a) in the desert of Oman consisting of two stages with VF beds and the irrigation field for treated effluent reuse (b).

Reference: Stefanakis, A.I., 2020. [Constructed Wetlands for Sustainable Wastewater Treatment in Hot and Arid Climates: Opportunities, Challenges and Case Studies in the Middle East](#). *Water* 2020, 12, 1665

Name	Forest habitat conservation
Description	Forest conservation involves the protection and maintenance of forests and their ecosystems, which can help address several aspects of land degradation. Land degradation is the decline in the quality and productivity of land, often caused by human activities such as deforestation, overgrazing, unsustainable agriculture and urbanisation.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change; Ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss; Natural disasters
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Decline in vegetation community functioning Decline in vegetation cover/ biomass/ biomass Habitat loss Increase in invasive species Soil organic matter decline Trees encroachment
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Agro-forestry; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Ecosystem-based fire management strategies; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land exclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Phytosanitary cutting; Protected areas; Reestablishment of landscape features (i.e. stone walls) and afforestation; Reserves, conservancies; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plan.
Examples	There is a need to improve the consistency of international information concerning the conservation status assessment of the

species and habitat types in the Natura 2000 reports. National Forest Inventories could contribute towards a more objective and harmonised assessment although their use shows some challenges as low precision for rare or small area habitats. Recommendations for a set of 12 structural and functional indicators are provided.

Reference: Alberdi I., Nunes L., Kovac M. et al., 2019. [*The conservation status assessment of Natura 2000 forest habitats in Europe: capabilities, potentials, and challenges of national forest inventories data*](#). Annals of Forest Science 76, 34 (2019).

Name	Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon)
Description	The Cocoon can be defined as an incubator for tree plantations as it protects the seedling, provides water and helps it to grow. It is a water-efficient, low-cost and biodegradable water bucket made from recycled cardboard and is 100% biodegradable, helping plants to survive and develop deep root systems in poor soils. The Cocoon can be seen as an eco-technology to support reforestation and agriculture, especially in arid and semi-arid regions.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation Protection Management Restoration Issue specific: Fire; Water management
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change, Natural disasters, Water security, Ecosystem degradation and Biodiversity loss
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (source NL4DL MM)	Change in groundwater level / quality Hydrological modification
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Land enclosures; Organic farming; Protected areas; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plan
Examples	The Green Link project aims to contribute to the development of effective adaptation strategies across the Mediterranean region by testing an innovative farming method to restore desertified areas. This consists of replacing traditional irrigation techniques with the Cocoon, a water-efficient, low-cost and 100% biodegradable system,

through six trials in three different Mediterranean countries suffering from desertification.

Name	<u>Reestablishment of landscape features (ie stone walls) and afforestation</u>
Description	The restoration of landscape features such as stone walls can help to halt land degradation through different mechanisms: soil erosion control; terracing; windbreaks; wildlife habitat; water management; cultural and historical significance; carbon sequestration; landscape aesthetics.
NBS main approach or purpose*	Creation/ Infrastructure Protection Management Restoration Issue specific
Potential co-benefits**	Climate change, Natural disasters, Water security, Ecosystem degradation and Biodiversity loss
Ecosystem***	Marine and coastal waters Heathlands and shrubs Bogs, mires, fens, and other wetlands Grasslands Other agroecosystems (incl croplands) Woodlands and forests Rocky habitats, dunes & sparsely vegetated lands Freshwater habitats (rivers and lakes) Others
Degradation process (NL4DL MM)	<u>Aridification</u> <u>Change in groundwater level / quality</u> <u>Increase in invasive species</u> <u>Increase in weeds</u> <u>Landscape modification</u> <u>Overgrazing</u> <u>Soil erosion by water and wind</u> <u>Soil surface compaction</u> <u>Trees encroachment</u>
NBS correlated	Afforestation of former grasslands; Agro-ecology; Constructed wetlands; Ecological restoration (functional and/or structural), Ecological Protection; Ecosystem-based management; Evolutionary-orientated forestry; Fire management strategies/seedling irrigation (Cocoon); Forest habitat conservation; Forestry nursery and afforestation; Green infrastructures; Habitat Restoration; Land enclosures; Managed rewilding; Natural systems agriculture; Organic farming; Protected areas; Reserves, conservancies; Soil and water bioengineering; Trapping sediment with vegetational measures; Water and forest management plan

Examples

Agricultural landscape features (LF) are small fragments of non-productive natural or semi-natural vegetation in the agricultural landscape that provide ecosystem services and support biodiversity. This definition includes several non-productive elements of traditional European agricultural landscapes, such as hedges, ponds, ditches, trees in rows, groups or isolated trees, field margins, terraces, dry stone or earth walls, planted areas, individual monumental trees, springs or historic canal networks. The role of LF on agricultural land is recognised in several key strategies and directives of EU environmental policy, such as the Biodiversity Strategy, the Water Framework Directive or the Nitrates Directive.

Source: Adobe Stock

Source: Adobe Stock

Czúcz B., Baruth B., Angileri V., Prieto Lopez A., Terres JM., 2022. [Landscape features in the EU Member States: A review of existing data and approaches](#). EUR 31063 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-52324-6

* The categorization of NBS approaches presented in this Catalogue is a reworking by the authors based on the categorizations of NBS approaches presented by the IUCN and by IPBES-IPCC. The IUCN, in its work on the Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions (IUCN,2020), proposes 5 categories of NBS approaches: protection, infrastructure, management, restoration, and issue specific. The two intergovernmental platforms IPBES and IPCC, in their [joint workshop report of 2021](#), recognize NBS as actions that yield benefits in addressing both climate change

and biodiversity loss, and categorize them as: protection, restoration, management, and creation. Hypothetically aligning the IPBES-IPCC category of creation with the IUCN's infrastructure category, the two categorizations proposed by these international organizations are assimilable, with the addition of the IUCN's issue-specific category, which concerns solutions for specific critical issues or domains (e.g., urban areas).

** According to the IUCN's definition of NBS (*Actions to protect, manage and restore natural or modified ecosystems, which address societal challenges, effectively and adaptively, providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits*), the Catalogue selected, as [potential co-benefits of the NBS](#), the societal challenges to which the definition above refers, which are: climate change, natural disasters, social and economic development, human health, food security, water security, ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss.

*** The Catalogue chooses to use the list of ecosystems present in the Prioritised Action Frameworks (PAFs) for financing Natura 2000. The Habitats Directive makes a clear link between the necessary conservation measures and the EU co-financing, and the PAFs are the instruments in charge of defining the funding needs and priorities for Natura 2000 at a national or regional level and potential sources of EU contribution. An [updated format](#) for PAFs was developed in 2018 and has been used by the Member States to prepare their PAFs for current multiannual financial framework (2021-2027). This format contains the list of ecosystems used here.

ANNEX B

Catalogue of Indexes/Indicators analysed in NL4DL project

Table 1. Spectral Indices from RS data: generic formulas adapted to Sentinel-2 bands and the connected degradation process are reported. R is the reflectance at the central wavelengths (nm) denoted by the subscripts.

Type	Name	Formula	Formula by Sentinel-2 bands	Reference	Degradation process
Vegetation Indices	NDVI Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	$\frac{R_{800} - R_{670}}{R_{800} + R_{670}}$	$\frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red}$	Rouse et al. (1974); Zarco-Tejada et al. (2001)	Decline in Biodiversity; Decline in Biomass; Decline in vegetation community functioning; Decline in vegetation cover
	GNDVI Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	$\frac{R_{800} - R_{550}}{R_{800} + R_{550}}$	$\frac{NIR - Green}{NIR + Green}$	Gitelson et al. (1996)	
	MSAVI2 Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	$\frac{2R_{800} + 1 - \sqrt{(2R_{800} + 1)^2 - 8(R_{800} - R_{670})}}{2}$	$\frac{2 * NIR + 1 - \sqrt{(2 * NIR + 1)^2 - 8 * (NIR - Red)}}{2}$	Qi et al. (1994)	
	OSAVI Optimized Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	$(1 + 0.16) \frac{R_{800} - R_{670}}{R_{800} + R_{670} + 0.16}$	$(1 + 0.16) \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red + 0.16}$	Rondeaux et al. (1996)	
	NDRE Normalized Difference Red-Edge	$\frac{R_{860} - R_{700}}{R_{860} + R_{700}}$	$\frac{NIR_{narrow} - RedEdge1}{NIR_{narrow} + RedEdge1}$	Zhang et al. (2019)	

	ARVI Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index	$\frac{R_{800} - [R_{670} - (R_{450} - R_{670})]}{R_{800} + [R_{670} - (R_{450} - R_{670})]}$	$\frac{NIR - [Red - (Blue - Red)]}{NIR + [Red - (Blue - Red)]}$	Bannari et al. (1995)	
	EVI2 Enhanced Vegetation Index2	$2.5 \frac{R_{800} - R_{670}}{R_{800} + 2.4R_{670} + 1}$	$2.5 \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + 2.4Red + 1}$	Jiang et al. (2008)	
	REP RedEdge Position	$705+35 \frac{\left(\frac{R_{670}+R_{780}}{2}\right) - R_{700}}{R_{740}+R_{700}}$	$705+35 \frac{\left(\frac{Red+RedEdge3}{2}\right) - RedEdge1}{RedEdge2+RedEdge1}$	Main et al. (2011)	
	NDMI Normalized Difference Moisture Index	$\frac{R_{860} - R_{1650}}{R_{860} + R_{1650}}$	$\frac{NIR_{narrow} - SWIR1}{NIR_{narrow} + SWIR1}$	Lastovicka et al., (2020)	
	PRI Photochemical Reflectance Index	$\frac{R_{531} - R_{570}}{R_{531} + R_{570}}$	$\frac{Blue - Green}{Blue + Green}$ Blue band is too large for accurate estimations	Gamon et al., (1992)	Decline in productivity
	LAI Leaf Area Index	SNAP ESA tool - derived product		https://step.esa.int/main/toolboxes/snap	
Water Indices	NDWI1 Normalized Difference Water Index 1	$\frac{R_{800} - R_{2130}}{R_{800} + R_{2130}}$	$\frac{NIR - SWIR2}{NIR + SWIR2}$	Gao, 1996; Chen et al., 2005	Decline in vegetation
	NDWI2 Normalized Difference Water Index 2	$\frac{R_{550} - R_{800}}{R_{550} + R_{800}}$	$\frac{Green - NIR}{Green + NIR}$	McFeeters (1996)	Hydrological modifications

	MNDWI Modified Normalized Difference Water Index	$\frac{R_{550} - R_{2130}}{R_{550} + R_{2130}}$	$\frac{Green - SWIR2}{Green + SWIR2}$	Xu (2006)	
Soil Indices	NDSI Normalized Difference Soil Index	$\frac{R_{1650} - R_{560}}{R_{1650} + R_{560}}$	$\frac{SWIR1 - Green}{SWIR1 + Green}$	Deng et al. (2015); Vibhute et al., 2017	Soil quality degradation
	NDBSI Normalized Difference Bare Soil Index	$\frac{R_{1650} - R_{860}}{R_{1650} + R_{860} + 0.001}$	$\frac{SWIR1 - NIR_{narrow}}{SWIR1 + NIR_{narrow} + 0.001}$	Chen et al. (2004)	
	BI Bare Index	$\frac{(R_{1650} + R_{670}) - (R_{800} + R_{450})}{(R_{1650} + R_{670}) + (R_{800} + R_{450})}$	$\frac{(SWIR1 + Red) - (NIR + Blue)}{(SWIR1 + Red) + (NIR + Blue)}$		
Burned Areas Indices	NBR Normalized Burn Ratio	$\frac{R_{860} - R_{2200}}{R_{860} + R_{2200}}$	$\frac{NIR_{narrow} - SWIR2}{NIR_{narrow} + SWIR2}$	Key et al. (2002)	Forest fires
	NBR2 Normalized Burn Ratio 2	$\frac{R_{1600} - R_{2200}}{R_{1600} + R_{2200}}$	$\frac{SWIR1 - SWIR2}{SWIR1 + SWIR2}$		
Soil Salinity Indices	SS1 Soil Salinity Index-2	$\sqrt{R_{[520:600]} * R_{[630:690]}}$	$\sqrt{Green * Red}$	Douaoui et al. (2006); Khan et al. (2001);-Yahiaoui et al. (2015)	Soil Salinization
	SS2 Soil Salinity Index-2	$2 * R_{[520:600]} - (R_{[630:690]} + R_{[770:900]})$	$2 * Green - (Red + NIR)$	Douaoui and Lepinard (2010); Yahiaoui et al. (2015)	

	SSI3 Soil Salinity Index-1	$\sqrt{R^2_{[630:690]} + R^2_{[520:600]}}$	$\sqrt{Red^2 + Green^2}$	Douaoui et al. (2006); Yahiaoui et al. (2015)	
	SI Soil Salinity	$\frac{R_{[530:590]} * R_{[640:670]}}{R_{[450:510]}}$	$\frac{Green * Red}{Blue}$	Elhag et al. (2016)	
	SASI Soil Adjusted Salinity Index	$\frac{R_{[630:690]}}{100 * R^2_{[450:520]}}$	$\frac{Red}{100 * Blue^2}$	Yahiaoui et al. (2015)	
Drought/ Dryness Indices	NDDI Normalized Difference Drought Index	$\frac{NDVI - NDWI_1}{NDVI + NDWI_1}$		Gu et al. (2007); Renza et al. (2010)	Aridification
	DSI Desertification Soil Index	$\frac{R_{1648} - R_{498}}{R_{1648} - R_{2203} + 0.2}$	$\frac{SWIR1 - Blue}{SWIR1 - SWIR2 + 0.2}$	Wu et al. (2010)	

Table 2. Indicators and their metric/measure useful for land degradation assessment.

Indicator	Sub-Indicator	Metric/Measure	Final Formula for sub-indicators	Reference	By RS data	Degradation process
SDG 15.3.1 proportion of land that is degraded	LC change (Trend in LC)	LC Area	<i>One Out, All Out</i>	UNCCD (2017; 2018; 2021); https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/metadata/files/Metadata-15-03-01.pdf	Yes	Habitat loss; Decline in productivity; Trees encroachment;
	Land Productivity loss	Net Primary Production (NPP)			Yes by proxies from RS	
	Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) decline	SOC				

over total land area	Further sub-indicators					Urban expansion.....
	Loss of habitat quality	Habitat cover Area	<i>One Out, All Out</i>	Assennato et al., 2020	RS (LC/habitat map)+InVEST model	
	Burnt Areas	LC Area			Yes	
	Fragmentation Index	Mesh density			RS (LC)+spatial rules	
	Areas of potential impact	LC Area			RS (LC)+spatial rules	
	Density of artificial LC	LC Density			Yes	
	Increasing of not sealed areas	LC Area			RS (LC)+spatial rules	
	OTHERS.....					
SDG 15.1.2 Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by PAs, by ecosystem type	Ecosystem within PA	LC/Habitat Area	<i>Coverage of an ecosystem within protected area Coverage of the Key Biodiversity Areas</i>	https://www.landportal.org/book/dataset/un-sdg1512	Yes	Conservation, restoration and sustainable use of ecosystems
	Key Biodiversity Areas (KBA)	World Database of Key Biodiversity Areas				

SDG 11.3.1 Ratio of land consumption rate to population growth rate	Land Consumption Rate	$\frac{\ln(Urb_{grid,t+n} / Urb_{grid,t})}{n}$ <p>Urb_{grid,t+n} = surface occupied by urban areas, in the output cell considered, at the final year (t+n).....</p>	<p>Land Consumption Rate - 11-03-2019.pdf;</p> <p>Aquilino et al. (2020)</p>	Yes	Urban expansion
	Population Growth Rate	$\frac{\ln(P_{grid,t+n} / P_{grid,t})}{n}$ <p>P_{grid,t+n} = population living in urban areas, in the output cell considered, at the final year (t+n).....</p>		No	
ESA(I) Environmentally Sensitive Areas to Desertification (Index)	Soil Quality Index (SQI)	(Soil Texture * Rock Fragment * Soil Depth * Parent Material * Drainage * Slope Gradient) ^{1/6}	$(SQI * CQI * VQI * MQI)^{\frac{1}{4}}$ <p>Tselimis et al. (2018)</p>	RS (slope)+ Ancillary data	Desertification
	Climate Quality Index (CQI)	(Rainfall * Aridity Index * Slope Aspect) ^{1/3}		RS (slope)+ Meteo data	
	Vegetation Quality Index (VQI)	(Fire Risk * Erosion Protection * Drought Resistance * Plant Cover) ^{1/4}		RS (vegetation cover; burned areas)+ Ancillary data	
	Management Quality Index (MQI)	(LU Intensity * Policy) ^{1/2}		RS (LC)+ Ancillary data	

SDVI Standardized Drought Vulnerability Index	cSPI6	Meteoreological - Hydrological - Agricultural Drought Vulnerability (Standard Precipitations over 6 months)	$SDVI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \text{Scaled Values of the Components}}{\text{Number of Components (N = 6)}}$	Karavitis et al. (2014); Tsemelis et al. (2018)	Meteo data+ Ancillary data	Drought
	cSPI12 (Standard Precipitations)	Meteorological - Hydrol. Drought Vulnerability (Standard Precipitations over 12 weeks)			No	
	Supply	Hydrological - Agricultural - Social Drought Vulnerability				
	Demand	Agricultural - Social Drought Vulnerability				
	Impacts	Social Drought Vulnerability				
	Infrastructure	Hydrological - Agricultural - Social Drought Vulnerability				

4. REFERENCES

- Canadian Parks Council, 2008. [*Principles and Guidelines for Ecological Restoration in Canada's Protected Natural Areas*](#). Parks Canada Agency Gatineau, Quebec.
- Cohen-Shacham E. et al. (eds), 2016. *Nature-based solutions to address global societal challenges*. xiii+97pp. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN.
- CREAF, 2021. [*Conclusions and recommendations report. LIFE The Green Link*](#).
- European Commission, 2020. *EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. Bringing nature back into our lives*. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions.
- European Commission EU, 2021. [*European Mission. A Soil Deal for Europe 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030 – Implementation Plan*](#).
- European Commission, 2022. [*Nature restoration law – For people, climate, and planet, Publications Office of the European Union*](#), 2022.
- FAO, 2020. *Protocol for the assessment of Sustainable Soil Management*. Rome, FAO.
- Fleskens L., 2019. *Sustainable Land Management (SLM) in Practice in the Kagera Basin: Lessons Learned for Scaling Up at Landscape Level*. By FAO, Mountain Research and Development 39(4).
- Haines-Young R., Potschin M., 2018. Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services, (CICES) V5.1. Guidance on the Application of the Revised Structure. Available at the following URL: <https://cices.eu/content/uploads/sites/8/2018/01/Guidance-V51-01012018.pdf>
- ISPRA, 2014. *Elementi per l'aggiornamento delle norme tecniche in materia di valutazione ambientale*. Manuali e linee guida 109/2014.
- IUCN, 2020. *Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions. A user-friendly framework for the verification, design and scaling up of NbS*. First edition. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN.
- Keenleyside K.A., N. Dudley, S. Cairns C.M. Hall, and S. Stolton, 2012. *Ecological Restoration for Protected Areas: Principles, Guidelines and Best Practices*. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN.
- MacKinnon K., van Ham C., Reilly K., Hopkins J., 2008. Nature-Based Solutions and Protected Areas to Improve Urban Biodiversity and Health. In Marselle M.R., Stadler J., Korn H., Irvine
- Mittermeier R.A., Totten M., Pennypacker L.L., Boltz F., Mittermeier C.G., Midgley G., Rodriguez C.M., Prickett G., Gascon C., Seligmann P.A. and Langrand O., 2008. *Climate for Life*, Washington DC: Conservation International.

National Parks Directorate Parks Canada Agency, 2008. *Principles and guidelines for ecological restoration in Canada's protected natural areas*. Quebec

Panagos, P., Van Liedekerke, M., Borrelli, P., Köninger, J., Ballabio, C., Orgiazzi, A., Lugato, E., Liakos, L., Hervas, J., Jones, A. Montanarella, L., 2022. European Soil Data Centre 2.0: Soil data and knowledge in support of the EU policies. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 73(6), e13315. DOI: 10.1111/ejss.13315

Rouse, J.W, Haas, R.H., Scheel, J.A., Deering, D.W., 1974. Monitoring Vegetation Systems in the Great Plains with ERTS. *Proceedings, 3rd Earth Resource Technology Satellite (ERTS) Symposium*, vol. 1, p. 48-62. <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/19740022614>

Running, S., R. R. Nemani, F. A. Heinsch, M. Zhao, M. Reeves, H. Hashimoto. 2004. A continuous satellite-derived measure of global terrestrial primary production. *BioScience*, 54(6): 547-560. 2004.

SER Society for Ecological Restoration (Gann GD, McDonald T, Walder B, Aronson J, Nelson CR, Jonson J, Hallett JG, Eisenberg C, Guariguata MR, Liu J, Hua F, Echeverría C, Gonzales E, Shaw N, Decler K, Dixon KW.), 2019. *International principles and standards for the practice of ecological restoration*. Second edition: November 2019. Society for Ecological Restoration, Washington, D.C. 20005 U.S.A.

Sims, N.C., Newnham, G.J., England, J.R., Guerschman, J., Cox, S.J.D., Roxburgh, S.H., Viscarra Rossel, R.A., Fritz, S. and Wheeler, I., 2021. [Good Practice Guidance. SDG Indicator 15.3.1. Proportion of Land That Is Degraded Over Total Land Area. Version 2.0](#). United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification, Bonn, Germany.

UNEA, 2022. Fifth session of the United Nations Environment Assembly. Resolution 5.

UNEP, 2021. *Making Peace with Nature—A scientific blueprint to tackle the climate, biodiversity, and pollution emergencies*. UNEP Secretariat, Nairobi.

Van Zanten B. T., Gutierrez G. G., Brander L. M., Gonzalez R. B., Griffin R., Macleod K. K., Alves Beloqui A. I., Midgley A., Herrera Garcia L. D., Jongman B., 2023. [Assessing the Benefits and Costs of Nature-Based Solutions for Climate Resilience: A Guideline for Project Developers](#). World Bank.